

The Division of Understanding: Specialization and Democratic Accountability^{*}

Giampaolo Bonomi[†]

April 13, 2026

Abstract

This paper studies how the organization of production shapes democratic accountability. I propose a model in which learning economies make specialization productively efficient: most workers perform one-domain tasks, while a small set of integrators with cross-domain knowledge keep the system coherent. When policy consequences run across domains, integrators understand them better than specialists. Electoral competition then tilts government policies toward integrators' interests, while low aggregate system knowledge weakens governance and reduces the fraction of public resources converted into citizen-valued services. Labor markets leave these civic margins unpriced, failing to internalize the political returns to system knowledge. Broadening specialists can therefore raise welfare relative to the market allocation. The model speaks to debates on liberal arts education and the effects of AI.

JEL Codes: D72, L22, J24, D83, H41.

Keywords: specialization; knowledge; voting; democratic accountability; AI.

^{*}I am grateful to Carlo Cusumano, Aram Grigoryan, Matias Iaryczower, Gleason Judd, Alessandro Lizzeri, John Londregan, Pietro Ortoleva, Kris Ramsay, and Joel Sobel for helpful comments and suggestions.

[†]Princeton University. Email: bonomi@princeton.edu

1 Introduction

“... as stupid and ignorant as it is possible for a human creature to become ... incapable of judging the great and extensive interests of his country.”

— Smith (1776, Book V, Ch. 1)

The division of labor is a classic engine of productivity gains. Narrower tasks allow most people to specialize and exploit learning economies, while coordination is delegated to a minority of individuals (Smith, 1776; Becker and Murphy, 1992). But Smith also worried that specialization carried a civic cost: people confined to narrow routine tasks might become less able to judge broader public interest questions. This paper formalizes a channel through which that concern can arise. While markets organize knowledge in ways that are efficient for production, democratic accountability may require a different allocation of knowledge. Specialization is therefore not only a division of tasks, but also a division of understanding, and that division can shape politics.

How we produce \implies What we know \implies How well we understand policy

Much like managing a productive organization requires knowledge of how its units interact, evaluating the consequences of policies requires knowledge that spans across different domains. A trade reform may appear to be a sectoral intervention, yet its consequences often ripple through complex supply chains, labor market adjustments, tax capacity, and regulatory enforcement. A climate or industrial policy may similarly operate through energy markets, procurement, permitting, fiscal transfers, and firm organization at once. In such cases, judging policy requires more than local expertise in one domain. It requires enough cross-domain knowledge to trace how changes in one part of the economy and society propagate through others.

Both in production and in politics, this cross-domain knowledge is scarce and unevenly distributed. In modular organizations, narrow specialists handle routine tasks within individual modules, while a smaller layer of integrators manages the handoffs, compatibility constraints, and exceptions that arise across modules (Garicano, 2000). In politics, citizens differ in their ability to integrate dispersed signals, expert claims, and institutional cues, a capacity that is scarce and unevenly distributed (Dewey, 1927; Lippmann, 1925; Hardwig, 1985; Lupia and McCubbins, 1998; Converse, 1964; Zaller, 1992; Delli Carpini and Keeter, 1996). This paper studies how the organization of production shapes citizens’ political understanding and, consequently, democratic accountability.

The paper’s mechanism runs in three steps. Productive efficiency creates a layered organization: routine production is assigned to narrow specialists, while coordination is

assigned to broader integrators whose knowledge is aligned with the interfaces created by specialization. Since understanding politics requires cross-domain knowledge, the same occupational structure then generates unequal *system knowledge* across citizens: integrators evaluate policy more precisely than specialists. In electoral competition, groups who evaluate policy more precisely receive greater political weight, while higher aggregate system knowledge in the electorate incentivizes politicians to design better policies, improving governance.

The central wedge follows immediately. Markets value knowledge for production, not for citizenship. As a result, they do not internalize either the governance return to aggregate system knowledge or the allocative inefficiency generated when such knowledge is concentrated in a small group that disproportionately affects policies. Welfare rises with aggregate system knowledge through governance and falls with its dispersion. The market allocation can therefore be productively efficient and yet civically inefficient.

To bring this wedge to light, I study the effects of reforms that broaden the pool of routine specialists while holding fixed what the economy is trying to produce. In particular, I compare the productively efficient knowledge distribution with slightly broader distribution of knowledge among workers who remain in routine roles. When integration is sufficiently efficient, the market demands only a thin layer of integrators. In that case, marginally broadening some specialists can raise aggregate system knowledge even though it modestly reduces productive specialization: the loss from shrinking an already small integrator layer is second-order, while the civic gain from broadening the large specialist mass is first-order. A natural interpretation is that institutions such as general-education requirements, cross-functional training, or other forms of curricular and occupational breadth may improve welfare not because broad workers are always more productive at routine tasks, but because broader citizens improve democratic accountability.

I offer a set of comparative statics to clarify when the political losses from specialization are likely to be largest. When politics becomes more about economic interfaces—that is, when understanding policy depends less on one local domain and more on tracing interactions across domains—the knowledge held by integrators becomes more politically valuable relative to the knowledge held by routine specialists. This can be read as a world of longer supply chains, layered regulation, industrial policy, climate policy, or other settings in which policy consequences propagate through different parts of the economy rather than within a single part. In those environments, the responsiveness gap between integrators and specialists widens, policy tilts further toward integrators, and the welfare losses associated with the political margins become larger. A distinct comparative static changes the efficiency of integration itself. When integration becomes more efficient, the

economy needs fewer integrators and produces more output. But because broad interface knowledge is then concentrated in a smaller share of citizens, democratic accountability may weaken. The welfare effect of changes in integration efficiency is therefore ambiguous even when the productive effect is not.

These mechanisms also provide a useful lens for two broader debates discussed later in the paper. One concerns liberal-arts education: if broad curricula raise system knowledge among citizens whose labor-market roles would otherwise be narrow, then they may generate civic returns that markets do not fully reward. The other concerns artificial intelligence: if AI mainly substitutes for specialist depth while leaving humans in integrative roles, it may strengthen accountability by effectively broadening access to relevant knowledge; if instead it substitutes for human integration or degrades the public information environment, its political effects may run in the opposite direction.

Taken together, the paper's main point is summarized by an intuitive observation: how we produce shapes what people learn, and what people learn shapes how well they understand and monitor policy. The paper's contribution is to provide a framework that makes it possible to study that sequence in a unified way, and thus to connect the organization of production, the distribution of politically useful knowledge, and democratic accountability within a single political-economic perspective.

The paper is structured as follows. Section 2 is a literature review. Section 3 defines system knowledge and the mapping from knowledge profiles to political understanding. Section 4 characterizes the efficient division of cognitive labor in production. Section 5 studies how the resulting distribution of knowledge shapes electoral competition and governance. Section 6 compares the market allocation to the civic optimum and develops the main comparative statics. Section 7 discusses implications for liberal education and artificial intelligence. Section 8 concludes.

2 Related literature

This paper relates first to the literature on the division of labor, organizational capabilities, and the organization of knowledge inside firms. Chandler (1992) emphasizes, from a business-history perspective, that the rise of the modern industrial enterprise rested on the accumulation of organizational capabilities. Becker and Murphy (1992) formalize the gains from specialization and the coordination costs that limit it. Most closely related is Garicano (2000), who studies knowledge hierarchies in which routine problems are handled by narrower workers and harder exceptions are escalated to more knowledgeable agents. A related literature studies firms as communication and information-processing

structures and analyzes the tradeoffs among specialization, coordination, adaptation, and broader task bundles (Radner, 1993; Bolton and Dewatripont, 1994; Dessein and Santos, 2006; Alonso et al., 2008; Lindbeck and Snower, 2000). I focus on organizational design in the presence of civic externalities, a different welfare problem. A productively efficient organization can be civically inefficient because markets do not internalize the political implications of skill formation. In that sense, I study the political economy of different organizational designs.

This paper also relates to the literature on noisy voting, probabilistic voting, and rational inattention (Lindbeck and Weibull, 1987; Matějka and McKay, 2015; Matějka and Tabellini, 2021). Most closely related, Matějka and Tabellini (2021) study electoral competition with rationally inattentive voters and show how selective attention can distort policy toward salient or intense interests. The contribution here is to give an economic origin to those differences in political precision. Voters are not simply exogenously inattentive. Their ability to evaluate policy is shaped upstream by occupational choices. The paper, therefore, links political efficacy with the labor-market allocation of knowledge.

Finally, the paper relates to the literature on information shortcuts, democratic delegation, and expert advice. Lupia (1994) shows that low-information voters can use credible cues to approximate the choices of better-informed voters, and Lupia and McCubbins (1998) argue more generally that citizens can learn from others when they can identify speakers who are both knowledgeable and trustworthy. A broader delegation literature studies how institutions are designed to make such delegation workable (Kiewiet and McCubbins, 1991; McCubbins et al., 1987). The paper is less optimistic about whether expertise by itself removes the information problem from the table. If broad system knowledge correlates with occupational background, as my model would imply, the conflict of interest between experts and non-experts may hinder information transmission (Crawford and Sobel, 1982).

3 Knowledge domains and system knowledge

This section introduces the knowledge object that links production and politics. Each individual allocates a unit learning budget across K knowledge domains and thereby chooses a profile $s_i = (s_{i1}, \dots, s_{iK}) \in \mathbb{R}_+^K$, where s_{ik} is usable knowledge in domain k . Knowledge acquisition is subject to

$$\sum_{k=1}^K \ell(s_{ik}) \leq 1, \tag{1}$$

where $\ell : [0, \infty) \rightarrow [0, \infty)$ is continuous, strictly increasing, and strictly concave, with $\ell(0) = 0$ and $\ell(1) = 1$. In addition, ℓ is continuously differentiable on $[0, 1]$, with $0 < \ell'(1)$ and $\ell'(0) < \infty$. Concavity captures learning economies: concentrating learning in one domain yields disproportionately more expertise in that domain.

Whenever $\|s_i\|_1 > 0$, let

$$\pi_i \equiv \frac{s_i}{\|s_i\|_1} \in \Delta^{K-1}$$

be the *direction* of individual i 's knowledge. Thus $\|s_i\|_1$ measures how much knowledge the individual has in total, while π_i measures how that knowledge is distributed across domains. Due to learning economies, narrow directions of knowledge are more scalable than broad directions of knowledge: for any $\pi \in \Delta^{K-1}$, let $H(\pi)$ denote the maximal feasible scale along direction π ; then $H(\pi) \leq 1$, with equality only at corners.

Two domain profiles summarize, respectively, the type of knowledge that matters in production and politics. The productive profile $q \in \text{int} \Delta^{K-1}$ describes the domain composition relevant for efficient routine production, as described in the next section. The civic profile $u \in \text{int} \Delta^{K-1}$ describes the domain composition relevant for evaluating policy: a citizen with knowledge aligned with u is better able to interpret the consequences of government action. To compare a worker's knowledge with either profile, define the coverage operator

$$\mathcal{C}(a, b) \equiv \sum_{k=1}^K \min\{a_k, b_k\} \quad (2)$$

for arbitrary nonnegative vectors $a, b \in \mathbb{R}_+^K$. If $\|a\|_1 = \|b\|_1 = M$, then $\mathcal{C}(a, b) = M - \frac{1}{2}\|a - b\|_1$. Coverage measures how much of a relevant bundle of domain knowledge an agent can effectively decode, given her learning choices.

System knowledge I define citizen i 's *system knowledge* as

$$B_i \equiv \|s_i\|_1^p \mathcal{C}(\pi_i, u), \quad p > 0, \quad (3)$$

with the convention that $B_i = 0$ when $\|s_i\|_1 = 0$. System knowledge is high when a citizen both knows a lot in total and knows it in the domains that matter for interpreting policy.

The exponent p governs how much overall depth, as opposed to domain alignment, sharpens political understanding. It is natural to think that p is positive but not large. Much like verifying a good mathematical proof is easier than writing it from scratch, one need not attend medical school to form a reasonable view about vaccines, and one need not be both a banker and a builder to understand that interest rates affect construction. A

small p captures that asymmetry: breadth in the relevant directions can matter politically even when citizens lack the specialist depth that production rewards.

4 Production and coordination

This section characterizes the efficient division of knowledge inside production. Learning economies make concentrated knowledge valuable, so routine production pushes workers toward narrow roles. But a specialist organization means that most individual workers do not carry the surrounding knowledge needed to handle cross-module spillovers on their own. The organization therefore solves two distinct problems. Specialists supply routine production knowledge. Integrators supply the cross-domain support needed to make that specialist organization workable. The distinction is task-based rather than technological: workers draw from the same domain menu, but the organization assigns their knowledge to different uses.

4.1 Production

Let \mathcal{S} denote the set of specialists and \mathcal{M} the set of integrators, with integrator mass $m \in [0, 1]$. Aggregate specialist knowledge is described by

$$S \equiv \int_{i \in \mathcal{S}} s_i di, \quad H^S \equiv \|S\|_1,$$

where H^S is the stock of specialist human capital and S captures how it is distributed across domains. Output is described by the following production technology,

$$Y = VC(S, H^S q). \tag{4}$$

Output depends on how well the specialist layer covers the domain mix required for production. Knowledge in excess of what routine production requires in one domain cannot fully compensate for missing knowledge in another, so for a given total stock of specialist knowledge, output is maximized when the aggregate specialist composition matches q . Integrators do not enter (4) directly; their role is to supply the coordination overhead that allows this specialist organization to operate.

4.2 Coordination burden

A specialist who is narrow relative to the organization’s overall mix can master a module efficiently, but must rely on others when routine work touches adjacent domains.

Specifically, specialist i operating in organization with specialist composition $\bar{\pi} \equiv \frac{S}{H^S} \in \Delta^{K-1}$ generates an external coordination requirement

$$\gamma_i \equiv \left(\|s_i\|_1 \bar{\pi} - s_i \right)^+, \quad (5)$$

where $+$ is taken componentwise. Note that the benchmark bundle $\|s_i\|_1 \bar{\pi}$ is the knowledge profile that would make worker i a same-scale miniature of the specialist organization. The gap γ_i can therefore be interpreted as the minimal external augmentation needed to make i locally self-sufficient.¹ Aggregate coordination needs are described by the gap vector

$$G \equiv \int_{i \in \mathcal{S}} \gamma_i di, \quad (6)$$

its total size $g \equiv \|G\|_1$ and, when $g > 0$, the normalized gap profile $h \equiv \frac{G}{g}$.

The pair (g, h) summarizes the organization’s coordination burden. The scalar g is the total mass of external support the specialist layer requires. The profile h is the domain composition of that missing bundle. In this sense, h is a reduced-form summary of the interface structure induced by specialization: the model tracks where support is missing by domain, rather than the full matrix of pairwise interfaces.²

4.3 Integration

Integration is the activity that absorbs the coordination burden created by specialization. I model it as a bundle-processing task. One unit of coordination requires domain knowledge in proportions h . An integrator can absorb coordination only to the extent that her knowledge profile contains that bundle, and the number of such bundles she can process

¹Equivalently,

$$\gamma_i = \|s_i\|_1 (\bar{\pi} - \pi_i)^+,$$

so a specialist generates less coordination burden the closer her own knowledge mix is to $\bar{\pi}$. Because $\|s_i\|_1 \bar{\pi}$ and s_i have the same total mass, $\|\gamma_i\|_1 = \frac{1}{2} \| \|s_i\|_1 \bar{\pi} - s_i \|_1 = \|s_i\|_1 (1 - \mathcal{C}(\pi_i, \bar{\pi}))$. Taking the positive part therefore counts only shortages, not offsetting surpluses elsewhere in i ’s profile. A narrow specialist may know more than the organizational average in her own module, but that surplus does not reduce the need for support when the task spills into domains she does not know. The relevant coordination object is therefore the worker’s domain-specific shortages, not her total deviation from the average bundle.

²A richer model could track pairwise interface burdens explicitly. The present benchmark compresses those burdens into a domain-level shortage profile h , which is the sufficient statistic needed for the planner’s problem. Our formulation is equivalent to assuming domains are connected in a dense production network, where interfaces between domains k and k' arise with probability $\bar{\pi}_k \bar{\pi}_{k'}$.

is limited by her scarcest relevant domain. Each integrator $i \in \mathcal{M}$ chooses a knowledge profile s_i under the same learning technology as everyone else, i.e. s_i must satisfy the learning constraint (1). Integrator i 's effective contribution to integration is

$$J_i = \min_{k:h_k>0} \frac{s_{ik}}{h_k}.$$

Thus J_i is the number of standardized coordination bundles h embedded in i 's knowledge profile. This formulation captures how integration requires the right composition of knowledge: missing relevant domains bottlenecks the whole bundle.³ Aggregating across integrators,

$$J \equiv \int_{i \in \mathcal{M}} J_i di$$

is the economy's total effective integration capacity. The economy is *integrated* if J is large enough to handle the total fragmentation g :

$$J \geq \theta g, \tag{7}$$

where $\theta > 0$ is an inverse measure of the efficiency of the integration technology. Condition (7) treats integrators as coordination overhead. Specialists generate routine output directly; integrators do not enter (4), but the specialist organization is feasible only if the integrator layer is large enough to absorb the coordination burden it creates.

4.4 Productive allocation

A feasible production allocation consists of an occupational partition $(\mathcal{S}, \mathcal{M})$ and knowledge profiles $\{s_i\}_{i \in \mathcal{S} \cup \mathcal{M}}$ such that every worker satisfies the learning constraint (1) and the induced organization satisfies the coordination feasibility condition (7). A productivity planner chooses such an allocation to maximize output:

$$\max_{(\mathcal{S}, \mathcal{M}, \{s_i\})} VC(\mathcal{S}, H^{\mathcal{S}} q) \quad \text{s.t.} \quad (1) \forall i, \text{ and } (7). \tag{8}$$

The planner trades off two margins. Making routine workers broader reduces coordination needs, but it also gives up the learning economies from concentrated knowledge. Using a separate layer of integrators preserves those learning economies, but it requires resources devoted to coordination rather than production. Our first result characterizes

³Appendix A.1 shows that, for a given gap profile h , the most effective integrator type chooses the learning profile $s_i = H(h)h$, so that efficient integration tracks the interfaces created by specialists.

the most productively efficient feasible allocation when integration is sufficiently efficient, so that one integrator can coordinate many specialists.

Theorem 1 (Efficient productive organization). *There exists a cutoff $\bar{\theta} > 0$ such that, if $\theta < \bar{\theta}$, any optimal allocation satisfies:*

(i) **Full specialists.** *Every specialist exhausts the learning constraint and specializes in a single domain: for each $i \in \mathcal{S}$ there exists $k(i)$ such that $s_i = e_{k(i)}$.*

(ii) **Alignment.** *The aggregate specialist composition equals the productive requirement:*

$$\bar{\pi} = q.$$

(iii) **Integration.** *All integrators exhaust the learning constraint and choose the unique efficient profile*

$$s_i = H(h^*)h^* \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{M},$$

with

$$h_k^* = \frac{q_k(1 - q_k)}{D(q)}, \quad (9)$$

where $D(q) \equiv 1 - \sum_{k=1}^K q_k^2$ measures how broadly the productive requirement profile spans domains. The integrator share is

$$m^* = \frac{\theta D(q)}{H(h^*) + \theta D(q)} < \frac{1}{3}, \quad (10)$$

and output is

$$Y^* = \frac{V H(h^*)}{H(h^*) + \theta D(q)}. \quad (11)$$

In Appendix A.1 I provide an explicit expression for $\bar{\theta}$.

The theorem delivers a layered organization. Routine output is cheapest when production knowledge is concentrated in narrow specialist roles. But such a specialist layer is locally non-self-sufficient: each specialist carries her own module and relies on external support for the rest of the organizational mix. Efficient integrators, therefore, choose the interface profile required to absorb the support burden created by specialization.

The optimal organization of production has an immediate political implication. Because the efficient organization assigns routine production to corner specialists and coordination to gap-matched integrators, it also pins down the knowledge profiles held by the two occupational groups. To compare the political knowledge of specialists and integra-

tors at the productive optimum, I impose one mild restriction on the civic environment and on the political penalty to breadth.

Assumption 1 (Diffuse civic relevance and a mild breadth penalty). *Let $u_{(1)} \leq \dots \leq u_{(K)}$ denote the ordered coordinates of u , and suppose $K \geq 3$.⁴ Assume*

$$0 < p < \frac{\log((u_{(1)} + u_{(2)})/u_{(K)})}{-\log(K \ell^{-1}(1/K))}.$$

Assumption 1 says that the civic environment is sufficiently diffuse, and that the political penalty to breadth is not so strong as to overturn the informational advantage of interface knowledge. The next result translates the knowledge profile induced at the productive optimum into a comparison of system knowledge.

Proposition 1 (Integrator civic advantage). *At the productive allocation characterized in Theorem 1, integrators have more system knowledge than specialists. Formally,*

$$B_M^q > B_S^q.$$

where B_M^q and B_S^q denote, respectively, the average system knowledge of integrators and specialists at the productive optimum.

In the productive optimum, specialists each understand one local slice of the economy, while integrators carry the broad interface profile needed to connect domains. When civic relevance profile is sufficiently diffuse, that interface profile is also more informative for politics, so productive efficiency itself generates an integrator civic advantage.

5 Politics

In this section, I take the occupational allocation generated in production as given and study how it shapes politics. Citizens care about targeted public services and private income, but they differ in how accurately they can judge policy. Higher system knowledge raises a citizen's ability to connect observed outcomes, public signals, and policy claims to the underlying consequences of government action. That matters politically through two channels. First, groups whose members evaluate policy more precisely respond more

⁴The restriction $K \geq 3$ is used only to obtain a clean lower bound on interface coverage. When $K = 2$, the model remains well defined, but the interface profile is degenerate: $h^*(q) = (\frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2})$ for every $q \in \text{int } \Delta^1$. Hence the integrator direction no longer depends on the productive profile q , and the relevant coverage term becomes $\mathcal{C}((\frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2}), u) = \frac{1}{2} + u_{(1)}$, rather than $u_{(1)} + u_{(2)}$.

strongly to platform changes, so parties place greater weight on them when competing in elections. Second, higher aggregate system knowledge improves a common governance margin by making poor performance easier to detect and punish, thereby increasing the fraction of public resources that is converted into citizen-valued services.

5.1 Platforms, targeted service, and governance

Two office-motivated candidates compete in an election where voting is driven by policy comparisons. Policy has two components: candidates simultaneously choose a governance quality level $e \geq 0$ and a gross spending share $z \in [0, 1]$, where z is the share of the public budget targeted to integrators, while $1 - z$ is the share targeted to specialists.

Let $\tau \in [0, 1)$ denote an exogenous proportional tax rate, so that the public budget is financed out of the tax base τY generated by gross output. Effective public resources are

$$\tilde{R} = G(e, Y),$$

where $G : \mathbb{R}_+^2 \rightarrow \mathbb{R}_+$ satisfies $G(e, Y) > 0$, $G_e(e, Y) > 0$, $G_Y(e, Y) \geq 0$, and $G_{ee}(e, Y) \leq 0$. Candidate $a \in \{L, R\}$ who proposes governance level e^a bears cost $c(e^a)$. The interpretation of governance quality is broad: higher e can reduce diversion, waste, or administrative slip-page, but it can also improve implementation or any common-interest surplus-generating policy more generally. What matters is that higher quality e increases the amount of effective public resources that ultimately reaches citizens. Per-capita services are

$$t_M(e, z) = \frac{z\tilde{R}}{m}, \quad t_S(e, z) = \frac{(1-z)\tilde{R}}{1-m}, \quad (12)$$

So that a citizen in occupation $g \in \{S, M\}$ who receives service $t_g(e, z)$ has utility

$$U_i = y_i + \log t_g(e, z). \quad (13)$$

The targeted-service interpretation is broad. The object t_g can represent administrative responsiveness, regulatory assistance, procurement access, extension services, compliance support, or other public inputs whose incidence is not captured by net income y .

Assumption 2 (Regular governance problem). *The cost function $c : \mathbb{R}_+ \rightarrow \mathbb{R}_+$ is twice continuously differentiable, strictly increasing, strictly convex, and satisfies $c'(0) = 0$ and $\lim_{e \rightarrow \infty} c'(e) = +\infty$. For every $Y > 0$, the map $e \mapsto \log G(e, Y)$ is twice continuously differentiable, strictly concave and satisfies the Inada conditions.*

5.2 Noisy policy assessments and political equilibrium

A citizen with higher system knowledge can better assess the payoff consequences of policies. Let (e^a, z^a) denote the platform proposed by candidate $a \in \{L, R\}$. Voter i 's deterministic payoff from candidate a and her noisy perception of that payoff are

$$U_i^a = y_i + \log t_g(e^a, z^a), \quad \tilde{U}_i^a = U_i^a + \varepsilon_{ia},$$

where $\varepsilon_{iL}, \varepsilon_{iR}$ are i.i.d. Type-I extreme value with scale parameter

$$\Lambda_i = \frac{\Lambda_0}{B_i}, \quad \Lambda_0 \geq 1. \quad (14)$$

Citizen i votes for candidate R if and only if $\tilde{U}_i^R > \tilde{U}_i^L$.

Let aggregate system knowledge be

$$B^{soc} \equiv \int_0^1 B_i di.$$

The next proposition characterizes the unique political equilibrium.

Proposition 2 (Political equilibrium). *Suppose $m \in (0, 1)$ and $B_S, B_M > 0$. Then the two-candidate game admits a unique pure-strategy equilibrium, and that equilibrium is symmetric. The following holds in equilibrium.*

(i) *The equilibrium policy platform (e^{pol}, z^{pol}) satisfies*

$$e^{pol} = e^*(Y, B^{soc}), \quad z^{pol} = \frac{mB_M}{B^{soc}}.$$

(ii) *Governance quality $e^*(Y, B^{soc})$ and effective resources $\mathcal{R}(Y, B^{soc}) \equiv \mathcal{G}(e^*(Y, B^{soc}), Y)$ are strictly increasing in aggregate system knowledge,*

$$e_B^*(Y, B^{soc}) > 0, \quad \mathcal{R}_B(Y, B^{soc}) > 0.$$

(iii) *Delivered services are tilted towards groups with more system knowledge, with*

$$t_g^{pol} = \frac{B_g}{B^{soc}} \mathcal{R}(Y, B^{soc}) \quad (15)$$

for each $g \in \{S, M\}$. Consequently, if $B_M > B_S$, then $z^{pol} > m$ and $t_M^{pol} > t_S^{pol}$.

Proposition 2 brings to light two key political margins. Relative system knowledge determines targeted incidence: the group with higher B_g receives more service per capita and greater political weight. Aggregate system knowledge determines governance: when B^{soc} is larger, candidates invest more in the common-interest margin and a larger share of gross public resources reaches citizens. Since in the productive optimum $B_M^q > B_S^q$, at that allocation public spending advantages integrators, $z^{pol} > m$.

Let \mathcal{A} denote a feasible productive allocation. In the remainder of the paper, when an object already defined in the model is written as a function of \mathcal{A} , it denotes the value of that object at allocation \mathcal{A} . Denote by $\mathcal{V}(\mathcal{A})$ the service welfare at allocation \mathcal{A} ,

$$\mathcal{V}(\mathcal{A}) \equiv (1 - m(\mathcal{A})) \log t_S^{pol}(\mathcal{A}) + m(\mathcal{A}) \log t_M^{pol}(\mathcal{A}), \quad (16)$$

The next proposition provides a convenient representation for $\mathcal{V}(\mathcal{A})$.

Proposition 3 (Service welfare). *For any feasible interior allocation \mathcal{A} ,*

$$\mathcal{V}(\mathcal{A}) = \log \mathcal{R}(Y(\mathcal{A}), B^{soc}(\mathcal{A})) - \mathcal{D}(\mathcal{A}), \quad (17)$$

where

$$\mathcal{D}(\mathcal{A}) \equiv \log B^{soc}(\mathcal{A}) - \left[(1 - m(\mathcal{A})) \log B_S(\mathcal{A}) + m(\mathcal{A}) \log B_M(\mathcal{A}) \right] \geq 0.$$

The dispersion term $\mathcal{D}(\mathcal{A})$ is zero if and only if $B_S(\mathcal{A}) = B_M(\mathcal{A})$.

Proposition 3 isolates the paper's core political wedge. Service welfare rises with aggregate system knowledge through the governance term $\log \mathcal{R}(Y, B^{soc})$, but it falls with the dispersion of system knowledge across groups because unequal knowledge tilts targeted services toward the better-informed group. When it comes to democratic accountability, there are two potential ways a society yields returns: the return to raising B^{soc} , and the return to compressing the gap between B_S and B_M .

Let $B^{\max}(u)$ denote the highest level of system knowledge a citizen can achieve the learning constraint.

Remark 1 (Civic benchmark). *Fix production output Y . Suppose a planner interested in maximizing utilitarian welfare can choose $B_S, B_M \leq B^{\max}(u)$ without affecting production. Then the planner sets $B_S = B_M = B^{\max}(u)$.*

Were it possible to raise and spread system knowledge without changing output, doing so would be welfare improving: equal knowledge eliminates the targeting distortion, and higher common knowledge enlarges the effective public resources that reach citizens.

6 Market inefficiency and welfare

While competitive markets internalize the production value of specialization and integration, they do not meaningfully internalize the civic value of system knowledge. I first provide sufficient conditions under which a competitive industry decentralizes the productive optimum, and show that in general, such a competitive allocation does not maximize utilitarian welfare. Then, I study the effects of a policy aimed at broadening specialists' knowledge, and derive sufficient conditions under which a civic planner prefers less specialization than the market outcome. Finally, I study how welfare changes when the political knowledge requirement becomes increasingly about economic integration.

6.1 Competitive implementation

In this section, I decentralize the productive allocation problem. Firms post specialist and integrator jobs, together with wages, and each job specifies the productive knowledge required by the position. Workers may choose any feasible skill profile before entering the labor market and then decide which job to target. Competitive wages reward only productive usefulness, not the civic value of breadth. Hence profiles that are not part of the cost-minimizing organization are weakly less attractive in equilibrium: they either are not demanded or can earn only weakly lower wages than the active jobs. The menu of active jobs can be summarized by the induced organizational design. Equivalently, one may read the same reduced form as firms choosing training after hiring. The allocation result is the same under either interpretation.

Let \mathcal{A} denote a feasible productive allocation, and write $V_g(\mathcal{A}) \equiv \log t_g^{pol}(\mathcal{A})$ for the political-equilibrium service utility of occupation $g \in \{S, M\}$. I assume that workers choose occupations and skills based on the net market wages for such occupational roles, obtained after applying the common tax rate τ to gross wages, and the role-specific utilities $V_M(\mathcal{A})$ and $V_S(\mathcal{A})$. The take-away of this paper would be even stronger if instead workers ignored such political continuation values in their occupational choice.

Definition 1 (Competitive equilibrium). *A competitive equilibrium consists of role net wages (w_S, w_M) for the active specialist and integrator jobs, firm entry and job designs, workers' skill and job choices, and an induced allocation \mathcal{A} such that: (i) given wages, each active firm chooses its job design and scale to maximize profits; (ii) free entry implies zero profits; (iii) given posted jobs, wages, and continuation values $V_g(\mathcal{A})$, each worker chooses a feasible skill profile and a job to maximize net wage plus continuation utility; and (iv) labor markets clear.*

Appendix C writes the firm's choice directly as the induced design (x, ν) ; this is with-

out loss, because any active job menu induces such a design, and any design can be decentralized as a menu of posted jobs to which workers self-select through education.

Let \mathcal{A}^q denote the productive optimum of Theorem 1. Note that at that allocation,

$$\Delta^q \equiv V_M(\mathcal{A}^q) - V_S(\mathcal{A}^q) = \log\left(\frac{B_M^q}{B_S^q}\right) > 0.$$

The equality follows from (15), and the inequality from Proposition 1. Let $\bar{\ell} \equiv \ell'(0)$ and $\bar{\Delta} \equiv \log\left(\frac{\bar{\ell}^p}{u(1)}\right)$, and let $\tilde{V} \equiv (1 - \tau)V$ denote net productivity. The following result tells us that competitive markets implement the productive optimum, provided that coordination is sufficiently efficient.

Theorem 2 (Competitive implementation). *Suppose $\theta < \bar{\theta}$ and $\Delta^q < \tilde{V}$. Then \mathcal{A}^q is an interior competitive allocation. If, in addition,*

$$\theta < \min\left\{\frac{\bar{\theta}\tilde{V}q_{(1)}}{2(\tilde{V} + \bar{\ell}\bar{\Delta})}, \frac{\tilde{V}q_{(1)}}{2\bar{\ell}\bar{\Delta}}\right\},$$

then \mathcal{A}^q is the unique interior competitive equilibrium allocation.

The inequality $\Delta^q < \tilde{V}$ guarantees that the productive optimum can be supported with positive role wages. The remaining inequalities make that support robust to all interior equilibrium wage ratios. The main take-away is that labor markets reward only knowledge that lowers firms' unit costs: knowledge that is useful mainly for democratic oversight remains unpriced.

6.2 The civic wedge

With the market result in hand, the remaining question is whether the productively efficient allocation is also welfare maximizing once politics is taken into account.

Fix any feasible interior allocation A . Given the labor-income tax rate $\tau \in [0, 1)$, total utilitarian welfare is

$$W(\mathcal{A}) = (1 - \tau)Y(\mathcal{A}) + V(\mathcal{A}).$$

The first term is the private-income component of welfare, while $V(\mathcal{A})$ is the public-service component already characterized in Section 5.

Given that τ is exogenous, one could instead absorb it into the reduced-form resource map \mathcal{G} ; It is kept explicit to distinguish the utility from income that from delivered public services.

Proposition 4 (Welfare decomposition). *For any differentiable family $\{\mathcal{A}_b\}_b$ of interior feasible allocations,*

$$\mathcal{W}'_b = \underbrace{\left[(1 - \tau) + \frac{\mathcal{R}_Y(Y_b, B_b^{soc})}{\mathcal{R}(Y_b, B_b^{soc})} \right] Y'_b}_{\text{productive effect}} + \underbrace{\frac{\mathcal{R}_B(Y_b, B_b^{soc})}{\mathcal{R}(Y_b, B_b^{soc})} B_b^{soc'}}_{\text{governance effect}} - \underbrace{\mathcal{D}'_b}_{\text{political-targeting effect}}, \quad (18)$$

where $\mathcal{D}_b \equiv \mathcal{D}(\mathcal{A}_b)$.

Proposition 4 decomposes the three channels through which productive designs affect welfare. The productive effect is the usual output channel. The governance effect captures how aggregate system knowledge changes the amount of effective public resources that reaches citizens. The political-targeting effect captures how the dispersion of system knowledge across groups changes targeted incidence. Since the last term enters as a dispersion penalty, low civic capacity can still generate large welfare losses even if targeted-service distortions are modest.

6.3 A broadening policy

To identify when the market fails and possible solutions to this failure, I consider a one-parameter family of allocations that broadens routine knowledge while holding the productive target fixed. This isolates the margin the paper cares about: replacing some extreme routine specialization with broader specialist roles without changing what the economy is trying to produce.

For each $b \in [0, 1]$, define $\mathcal{A}(b)$ as follows. Among specialists, a share $1 - b$ are corner experts assigned across domains in proportions q_k , while a share b are broadened specialists with profile $H(q)q$. As in the market equilibrium, integrators are employed at the minimal feasible mass, and their knowledge matches the aggregate organizational gap.

This family has a natural policy interpretation. The parameter b captures reforms that broaden routine knowledge without changing the economy's productive objective: general-education requirements, cross-functional training, certification standards, or subsidies to transferable competence. Because broadening changes both the composition of specialists' knowledge and the total stock of knowledge they can sustain, the sign of $(B^{soc})'(0)$ is economically meaningful rather than mechanical: it depends on whether the civic gain from broadened specialists outweighs the civic loss from the marginal integrators that broadening makes unnecessary.

Theorem 3 (Excess specialization). *Suppose that the breadth penalty p is not too large, so that a broadened specialist with profile $H(q)q$ has more system knowledge than the average corner specialist,⁵ that is,*

$$H(q)^p C(q, u) > q \cdot u.$$

Then, for sufficiently small θ , a marginal broadening reform raises aggregate civic capacity:

$$\left. \frac{dB^{soc}(b)}{db} \right|_{b=0} > 0.$$

If, in addition,

$$\frac{\mathcal{R}_B(Y(0), B^{soc}(0))}{\mathcal{R}(Y(0), B^{soc}(0))}$$

is sufficiently large, then

$$\mathcal{W}'(0) > 0.$$

Hence, some broadening $b > 0$ improves welfare relative to the competitive benchmark.

Broadening has two opposing civic effects. It raises the civic capacity of routine workers, but it also shrinks the integrator layer. When θ is small, the benchmark integrator layer is thin, so little interface knowledge is lost at the margin. In that case, if a broadened specialist is civically more capable than a corner specialist—which is guaranteed if p is not too large—aggregate civic capacity rises. The reform improves the governance term $\log \mathcal{R}(Y, B^{soc})$, while any remaining targeting effect operates only through the dispersion term \mathcal{D} . If the governance return to civic capacity is sufficiently strong, that gain outweighs the productive loss from weaker learning economies. The deeper point is that broad knowledge is a form of organizational capital for the polity: it is costly to create, but it affects how effectively fiscal resources are turned into citizen-valued services.

6.4 Politics about economic integration

When does politics reward routine local knowledge and when does it reward cross-domain interface knowledge? Two primitive objects determine the answer. First, the production profile q describes where routine productive effort is concentrated in the economy. Second, the civic profile u describes what kinds of knowledge a voter needs in order to judge policy. In other words, does evaluating government mainly require understanding one local margin, or tracing how budgeting, regulation, procurement, and enforcement interact? Political distortion turns on how these two profiles line up. Under the productive

⁵Because $q, u \in \text{int } \Delta^{K-1}$ imply $C(q, u) > q \cdot u$, the condition $H(q)^p C(q, u) > q \cdot u$ is equivalently a small- p restriction: $p < \bar{p}_B(q, u) \equiv \log(C(q, u)/(q \cdot u))/(-\log H(q))$.

optimum, specialists inherit the routine profile q , while integrators inherit the interface profile $h^*(q)$ from Theorem 1. The key structural fact is that $h^*(q)$ is a flattening of q : relative to specialists, integrators put less weight on dominant production domains and more weight on secondary domains that matter when interactions become important.

Proposition 5 (Interface-intensive politics). *For the family*

$$u_\alpha = (1 - \alpha)q + \alpha h^*(q), \quad \alpha \in [0, 1], \quad (19)$$

evaluated at the productive allocation associated with q and θ , specialists' average system knowledge is weakly decreasing in α , and strictly decreasing if q is non-uniform. Integrators' average system knowledge is weakly increasing in α , and strictly increasing if q is non-uniform. If q is non-uniform, then for all sufficiently small θ ,

$$\frac{dB^{\text{soc}}}{d\alpha} < 0 \quad \text{and} \quad \frac{d\mathcal{W}}{d\alpha} < 0.$$

A higher α makes the civic environment more interface-intensive: understanding policy depends less on following one routine domain and more on tracing how domains interact. This always lowers specialists' average system knowledge and raises integrators'. Whether aggregate system knowledge rises or falls then depends on how large the integrator layer already is. When θ is small, the integrator layer is thin, so the first-order effect of a rise in α is to lower the political understanding of the large specialist majority. Aggregate system knowledge therefore falls. Welfare then moves through two margins. The governance margin is negative because lower aggregate system knowledge increases leakage. The political-targeting margin reflects the stronger electoral weight of integrators, but when θ is small that group is itself small, so this margin is second-order. Hence welfare also falls for sufficiently small θ . In practice, a higher α captures changes such as longer supply chains, layered regulation, industrial policy, climate policy, or trade conflicts, with consequences propagating through the economic system.

A distinct comparative static changes the efficiency of integration itself, holding both the productive profile q and the civic environment u fixed.

Proposition 6 (Changes in the efficiency of integration). *Fix q and u , and let $\mathcal{A}^q(\theta)$ denote the productive allocation characterized in Theorem 1. Then the equilibrium share of integrators $m^q(\theta)$ is strictly increasing in θ , equilibrium output $Y^q(\theta)$ is strictly decreasing in θ , and aggregate system knowledge $B^{\text{soc}}(\mathcal{A}^q(\theta))$ is strictly increasing in θ . The welfare effect of a change in θ is in general ambiguous.*

A higher θ means that each unit of cross-domain fragmentation absorbs more integrator effort. The economy therefore reallocates labor from routine production to interface management. This lowers output but spreads interface knowledge across a larger share of the electorate, raising aggregate system knowledge. Welfare is ambiguous because the productive loss and the accountability gain move in opposite directions, and the induced change in political targeting need not have a common sign. Economically, this comparative static captures changes in interoperability, modularity, management, or information technology that make integration easier or harder.

7 Discussion

This paper speaks to two broader debates that are often treated separately from the theory of the firm: the debate over the value of liberal-arts education, and the debate over the political economic implication of artificial intelligence.

7.1 Liberal-arts education

The model offers one way to organize the debate over the value of liberal-arts colleges and, more broadly, liberal education. One side of that debate emphasizes breadth: liberal education exposes students to multiple knowledge domains, develops habits of interpretation and argument, and prepares them for citizenship rather than only for a narrowly defined occupation (Nussbaum, 2010; Zakaria, 2015). Another side is more skeptical, either because colleges may generate limited measured learning gains relative to their aspirations (Arum and Roksa, 2011) or because a substantial share of the private return to college may reflect signaling rather than socially productive human-capital accumulation (Caplan, 2018). The mechanism in this paper is closest to the first view, but it provides a more specific welfare channel.

In the model, broad knowledge matters because some political questions require tracing indirect effects across domains. If liberal-arts institutions broaden students' knowledge profiles—raising coverage of the domains relevant for interpreting public problems—then they increase system knowledge even when labor markets do not fully reward that breadth. In the notation of Section 6, one can think of liberal education as moving some workers away from extreme corner specialization and toward broader profiles, for instance along the same margin studied in Theorem 3. The resulting gain need not appear fully in wages because firms internalize the production value of specialization but not the democratic value of broader evaluation and monitoring.

The takeaway is not that liberal-arts education is unequivocally welfare-improving, nor that every broad curriculum has the same social value. It is that broad education can, under some conditions, take care of a civic externality. Institutions that require exposure outside a student’s eventual occupation—general-education requirements, distribution requirements, and liberal-arts curricula more generally—may raise welfare by increasing the share of citizens who can evaluate cross-domain issues. With this reading, the strongest defense of liberal education is not only labor-market adaptability, but rather that democratic accountability may work better when more citizens can understand policy problems whose consequences run across domains. That logic is especially strong when civic relevance u is diffuse and when the productivity cost of additional breadth is modest relative to the democratic accountability gains.

7.2 Artificial intelligence

The model also provides one way to think about artificial intelligence and chatbots. A task-based view of technology emphasizes that automation changes the assignment of tasks rather than simply eliminating work outright (Acemoglu and Restrepo, 2019). Recent evidence on generative AI is consistent with that interpretation. In both customer-support and writing settings, AI systems appear able to codify and supply specialist knowledge in real time, with especially large gains for less experienced workers (Brynjolfsson et al., 2025; Noy and Zhang, 2023). At the same time, the evidence also suggests a “jagged technological frontier”: AI is highly useful on some knowledge tasks, but less reliable on others, so human judgment remains valuable precisely where workflows require cross-step integration or careful exception handling (Dell’Acqua et al., 2026). In the language of this paper, AI may compress part of the specialist layer without eliminating the integrator role.

A useful polar benchmark pushes that logic to its limit. Suppose AI is primarily a substitute for specialist knowledge, so that each citizen can supervise a portfolio of specialist AI agents at negligible civic cost. Then the pre-AI productive allocation \mathcal{A}^q provides a template for the AI era: each human citizen becomes an integrator, and each one manages $\frac{1-m^q}{m^q}$ specialist AI agents whose aggregate knowledge distribution matches q . Because the AI specialists neither vote nor enter welfare directly, only the human integrators matter politically. Since Proposition 1 implies $B_M^q > B_S^q$, replacing human specialists with AI specialists raises the average system knowledge of the voting population from

$$B^{soc,q} = (1 - m^q)B_S^q + m^q B_M^q$$

toward B_M^q . In that polar case the responsiveness distortion disappears among humans, leakage may fall, and the advent of AI is welfare improving.

That optimistic conclusion, however, depends on what AI actually substitutes for. If AI mainly replaces narrow specialist depth while leaving human integrative judgment central, then the model points toward welfare gains. But if AI also substitutes for integrative reasoning, degrades the public information environment, or floods citizens with low-quality signals, then the same technology could reduce rather than increase democratic accountability. More generally, the model suggests that the right question is not whether AI is good or bad for democracy in the abstract, but how AI changes the distribution of politically useful knowledge across citizens and whether it makes cross-domain policy consequences easier or harder to interpret.

8 Conclusion

The paper's main point is that specialization changes not only how production is organized, but also who can evaluate complex government action. Learning economies make narrow roles efficient inside firms, yet the resulting allocation of knowledge can leave only a subset of workers able to trace cross-domain consequences and monitor policy implementation. Accountability then weakens in two ways. Electoral competition places greater weight on groups whose members evaluate policy more precisely, and low aggregate system knowledge reduces delivery efficiency by making poor governance harder to detect and punish.

The model isolates this mechanism by linking production and politics through the same underlying object: a worker's knowledge profile. In production, efficient organizations combine narrow specialists with integrators who hold the knowledge needed to manage interfaces across modules. In politics, those same knowledge differences shape political responsiveness and monitoring. A civic planner therefore values broader knowledge not only because it supports coordination inside production, but also because it affects who is politically influential and how effectively public resources are turned into delivered services.

The comparative statics suggest that globalization, outsourcing, digitization, and regulatory layering can raise the political value of interface knowledge by making policy consequences run through interactions across domains rather than through one local margin. In such environments, integrators can become a small but politically influential group, and otherwise similar democracies can differ sharply in effective fiscal capacity if they differ in aggregate system knowledge. The policy implication is that civic capacity should

be treated more like an economic input. Transparency and formal oversight remain important, but so do investments and institutions that broaden citizens' domain coverage or make public information easier to interpret. In that sense, the civic costs of specialization are part of the allocation problem itself, not outside the economy.

References

- Acemoglu, D. and Restrepo, P. (2019). Automation and new tasks: How technology displaces and reinstates labor. *Journal of Economic Perspectives*, 33(2):3–30.
- Alonso, R., Dessein, W., and Matouschek, N. (2008). When does coordination require centralization? *American Economic Review*, 98(1):145–179.
- Arum, R. and Roksa, J. (2011). *Academically Adrift: Limited Learning on College Campuses*. University of Chicago Press, Chicago.
- Becker, G. S. and Murphy, K. M. (1992). The division of labor, coordination costs, and knowledge. *Quarterly Journal of Economics*, 107(4):1137–1160.
- Bolton, P. and Dewatripont, M. (1994). The firm as a communication network. *Quarterly Journal of Economics*, 109(4):809–839.
- Brynjolfsson, E., Li, D., and Raymond, L. R. (2025). Generative AI at work. *Quarterly Journal of Economics*, 140(2):889–942.
- Caplan, B. (2018). *The Case against Education: Why the Education System Is a Waste of Time and Money*. Princeton University Press, Princeton, NJ.
- Chandler, A. D. (1992). Organizational capabilities and the economic history of the industrial enterprise. *Journal of Economic Perspectives*, 6(3):79–100.
- Converse, P. E. (1964). The nature of belief systems in mass publics. In Apter, D. E., editor, *Ideology and Discontent*, pages 206–261. Free Press.
- Crawford, V. P. and Sobel, J. (1982). Strategic information transmission. *Econometrica*, 50(6):1431–1451.
- Dell'Acqua, F., McFowland III, E., Mollick, E., Lifshitz-Assaf, H., Kellogg, K. C., Rajendran, S., Kraymer, L., Candelon, F., and Lakhani, K. R. (2026). Navigating the jagged technological frontier: Field experimental evidence of the effects of artificial intelligence on knowledge worker productivity and quality. *Organization Science*, 37(2):403–423.

- Delli Carpini, M. X. and Keeter, S. (1996). *What Americans Know about Politics and Why It Matters*. Yale University Press.
- Dessein, W. and Santos, T. (2006). Adaptive organizations. *Journal of Political Economy*, 114(5):956–995.
- Dewey, J. (1927). *The Public and Its Problems*. Henry Holt.
- Garicano, L. (2000). Hierarchies and the organization of knowledge in production. *Journal of Political Economy*, 108(5):874–904.
- Hardwig, J. (1985). Epistemic dependence. *Journal of Philosophy*, 82(7):335–349.
- Kiewiet, D. R. and McCubbins, M. D. (1991). *The Logic of Delegation: Congressional Parties and the Appropriations Process*. University of Chicago Press, Chicago.
- Lindbeck, A. and Snower, D. J. (2000). Multitask learning and the reorganization of work: From tayloristic to holistic organization. *Journal of Labor Economics*, 18(3):353–376.
- Lindbeck, A. and Weibull, J. W. (1987). Balanced-budget redistribution as the outcome of political competition. *Public Choice*, 52(3):273–297.
- Lippmann, W. (1925). *The Phantom Public*. Harcourt, Brace.
- Lupia, A. (1994). Shortcuts versus encyclopedias: Information and voting behavior in california insurance reform elections. *American Political Science Review*, 88(1):63–76.
- Lupia, A. and McCubbins, M. D. (1998). *The Democratic Dilemma: Can Citizens Learn What They Need to Know?* Cambridge University Press.
- Matějka, F. and McKay, A. (2015). Rational inattention to discrete choices: A new foundation for the multinomial logit model. *American Economic Review*, 105(1):272–298.
- Matějka, F. and Tabellini, G. (2021). Electoral competition with rationally inattentive voters. *Journal of the European Economic Association*, 19(3):1899–1935.
- McCubbins, M. D., Noll, R. G., and Weingast, B. R. (1987). Administrative procedures as instruments of political control. *Journal of Law, Economics, and Organization*, 3(2):243–277.
- Noy, S. and Zhang, W. (2023). Experimental evidence on the productivity effects of generative artificial intelligence. *Science*, 381(6654):187–192.

Nussbaum, M. C. (2010). *Not for Profit: Why Democracy Needs the Humanities*. Princeton University Press, Princeton, NJ.

Radner, R. (1993). The organization of decentralized information processing. *Econometrica*, 61(5):1109–1146.

Smith, A. (1776). *An Inquiry into the Nature and Causes of the Wealth of Nations*. W. Strahan and T. Cadell.

Zakaria, F. (2015). *In Defense of a Liberal Education*. W. W. Norton & Company, New York.

Zaller, J. (1992). *The Nature and Origins of Mass Opinion*. Cambridge University Press.

A Productive organization

This appendix collects the proofs for the production block (Theorem 1). It begins from the *general* planner problem—allowing arbitrary specialist mastery profiles and arbitrary integrator deployments—and derives the “corner specialists + gap-matched integrators” structure from primitives. It then uses the implied reduced-form representation indexed by the aggregate specialist composition x to solve for the productive optimum.

Lemma 1 (Coverage distance identity). *For any $a, b \in \mathbb{R}_+^K$ with $\|a\|_1 = \|b\|_1 = M$,*

$$\mathcal{C}(a, b) = M - \frac{1}{2}\|a - b\|_1.$$

In particular, if $a, b \in \Delta^{K-1}$,

$$\mathcal{C}(a, b) = 1 - \frac{1}{2}\|a - b\|_1.$$

Proof. Let $c_k = \min\{a_k, b_k\}$. Then $a_k - c_k = (a_k - b_k)_+$ for each k , so

$$\sum_{k=1}^K c_k = \sum_{k=1}^K a_k - \sum_{k=1}^K (a_k - b_k)_+ = M - \sum_{k=1}^K (a_k - b_k)_+.$$

Since $\sum_k (a_k - b_k) = 0$, we have $\sum_k (a_k - b_k)_+ = \sum_k (b_k - a_k)_+ = \frac{1}{2} \sum_k |a_k - b_k|$, yielding the claim. ■

A.1 Productive optimum

The first step is to show that the “corner specialists + gap-matched integrators” structure follows from the productivity planner’s problem when learning economies are strong enough relative to the scale-sensitive coordination burden.

A.1 Efficient integrators and binding feasibility. Fix any feasible production allocation $(\mathcal{S}, \mathcal{M}, \{s_i\}_{i \in \mathcal{S} \cup \mathcal{M}})$ and suppose that total fragmentation is strictly positive, $g > 0$. Let $h \equiv G/g$ denote the normalized gap profile.

Lemma 2 (Upper bound on integrator contribution). *Fix a gap profile $h \in \Delta^{K-1}$. For any feasible profile $s \neq 0$ with direction $\pi = s/\|s\|_1$,*

$$\|s\|_1 \min_{k: h_k > 0} \pi_k / h_k \leq H(h),$$

with equality if and only if $s = H(h)h$.

Proof. Let $r = \|s\|_1$ and $c = \min_{k: h_k > 0} \pi_k / h_k$. Then $\pi_k \geq ch_k$ for every coordinate with $h_k > 0$, so $rch_k \leq r\pi_k = s_k$ coordinatewise. Since ℓ is increasing,

$$\sum_{k=1}^K \ell(rch_k) \leq \sum_{k=1}^K \ell(s_k) \leq 1.$$

Hence rc is feasible along direction h , which implies $rc \leq H(h)$. This gives the inequality.

If $s = H(h)h$, then $r = H(h)$ and $c = 1$, so equality holds. Conversely, suppose equality holds. Then $rc = H(h)$. Since $H(h)$ is feasible along direction h , by definition $\sum_{k=1}^K \ell(rch_k) = \sum_{k=1}^K \ell(H(h)h_k) = 1$. Combined with $\sum_{k=1}^K \ell(rch_k) \leq \sum_{k=1}^K \ell(s_k) \leq 1$, this implies $\sum_{k=1}^K \ell(s_k) = \sum_{k=1}^K \ell(rch_k)$. But we already know that $rch_k \leq s_k$ for every k . Since ℓ is strictly increasing, equality of the sums can hold only if $s_k = rch_k$ for every k . Therefore $\pi_k = \frac{s_k}{r} = ch_k$ for every k . Summing over k gives

$$1 = \sum_{k=1}^K \pi_k = c \sum_{k=1}^K h_k = c,$$

so $c = 1$ and hence $\pi = h$. Since $rc = H(h)$, it follows that $r = H(h)$ and $s = H(h)h$. ■

Lemma 3 (Feasible positive-output benchmark). *There exists a feasible allocation with strictly positive output. In particular, the corner-specialist, gap-matched allocation with aggregate spe-*

cialist mix q and integrator share

$$m_q \equiv \frac{\theta D(q)}{H(h^\star) + \theta D(q)} \quad \text{with} \quad h_k^\star = \frac{q_k(1 - q_k)}{D(q)}$$

is feasible and yields

$$Y_q = \frac{VH(h^\star)}{H(h^\star) + \theta D(q)} > 0.$$

Consequently every productive optimum has strictly positive output.

Proof. Take a mass $1 - m_q$ of specialists, assigned to domains $k = 1, \dots, K$ in shares q_k , with each specialist holding the unit corner profile e_k . Then aggregate specialist knowledge is

$$S = (1 - m_q)q, \quad H^S = 1 - m_q = \frac{H(h^\star)}{H(h^\star) + \theta D(q)}, \quad \bar{\pi} = q.$$

Hence output is

$$Y = VC(S, H^S q) = VC((1 - m_q)q, (1 - m_q)q) = V(1 - m_q) = \frac{VH(h^\star)}{H(h^\star) + \theta D(q)} > 0.$$

Now compute the coordination burden. A specialist assigned to domain k has gap vector $(q - e_k)^+$, whose contribution to aggregate gaps is weighted by the specialist mass $(1 - m_q)q_k$. Summing across domains gives aggregate gap vector

$$G = (1 - m_q)(q \odot (1 - q))$$

and total gap mass

$$g = (1 - m_q)D(q).$$

Let every integrator choose the full-budget profile $H(h^\star)h^\star$. By Lemma 2, each such integrator contributes exactly $H(h^\star)$, so aggregate integration capacity is $J = m_q H(h^\star)$. By construction,

$$J = m_q H(h^\star) = \theta(1 - m_q)D(q) = \theta g,$$

so the allocation is feasible.

Since this feasible allocation yields strictly positive output, any productive optimum must also yield strictly positive output. ■

Lemma 4 (Integrators are efficient). *In any productive optimum with $g > 0$, almost every*

integrator exhausts the learning constraint and satisfies $s_i = H(h)h$. Consequently

$$J = mH(h).$$

Proof. Fix a productive optimum with $g > 0$. By Lemma 2, each integrator contributes at most $H(h)$, with equality if and only if she chooses the full-budget profile $H(h)h$. Suppose a positive-measure set of integrators contributes strictly less than $H(h)$. Replacing those integrators by the profile $H(h)h$ leaves specialists, gaps, and output unchanged, but strictly raises total integration capacity J . Therefore the modified allocation remains feasible and has $J' > J \geq \theta g$.

Now the modified allocation has slack integration capacity. Let $\bar{\pi} = S/H^S$. By Lemma 3, every productive optimum has strictly positive output. Since

$$Y = VH^S\mathcal{C}(\bar{\pi}, q),$$

this implies $\mathcal{C}(\bar{\pi}, q) > 0$. Move a sufficiently small positive mass of integrators into specialization and assign them profile $\delta\bar{\pi}$, where $\delta > 0$ is small enough to satisfy the learning constraint. These new specialists generate zero additional gaps, so g is unchanged, while specialist mastery and output rise strictly. This contradicts optimality. ■

Lemma 5 (Binding of the integration constraint). *In any productive optimum with $g > 0$, the integration constraint binds:*

$$mH(h) = \theta g.$$

Proof. Fix a productive optimum with $g > 0$ and suppose, to obtain a contradiction, that $mH(h) > \theta g$. Let $\bar{\pi} = S/H^S$ denote the aggregate specialist mix. Because $g > 0$, we have $H^S > 0$. By Lemma 3, every productive optimum has strictly positive output. Since

$$Y = V\mathcal{C}(S, H^S q) = VH^S\mathcal{C}(\bar{\pi}, q),$$

this implies $\mathcal{C}(\bar{\pi}, q) > 0$.

Pick $\varepsilon > 0$ small enough that $(m - \varepsilon)H(h) \geq \theta g$, and move a mass ε of workers from integration to specialization. Assign each of these new specialists the skill profile $s = \delta\bar{\pi}$ for some $\delta > 0$ small enough that $\sum_k \ell(\delta\bar{\pi}_k) \leq 1$. This perturbation increases aggregate specialist stock by $\varepsilon\delta\bar{\pi}$, hence strictly increases H^S while leaving $\bar{\pi}$ unchanged. At the same time, a specialist with profile proportional to $\bar{\pi}$ generates zero gaps, so G and g are unchanged. Feasibility is preserved because the post-perturbation integrator block still satisfies $(m - \varepsilon)H(h) \geq \theta g$.

Because $\bar{\pi}$ is unchanged,

$$Y' = V(H^S + \varepsilon\delta)\mathcal{C}(\bar{\pi}, q) > VH^S\mathcal{C}(\bar{\pi}, q) = Y.$$

Thus the original allocation cannot be optimal, proving that $mH(h) = \theta g$ in any productive optimum. ■

A.2 Learning frontiers and budget exhaustion. Fix a direction $\pi \in \Delta^{K-1}$ and write $\lambda(\pi) = 1/H(\pi)$ for the associated *relative inefficiency index*. Recall the (Euclidean) *fragmentation index* $D(\pi) \equiv 1 - \|\pi\|_2^2 \in [0, 1]$.

Lemma 6 (Corners maximize scale). *For every $\pi \in \Delta^{K-1}$,*

$$H(\pi) \leq 1,$$

with equality if and only if $\pi = e_k$ for some k . Equivalently, $\lambda(\pi) \geq 1$ with equality if and only if π is a corner.

Proof. Fix $\pi \in \Delta^{K-1}$ and $H \geq 0$. By concavity of ℓ and $\ell(0) = 0$, we have $\ell(\pi_k H) \geq \pi_k \ell(H)$ for each k . Summing and using $\sum_k \pi_k = 1$ yields

$$\sum_{k=1}^K \ell(\pi_k H) \geq \ell(H).$$

Hence if $\sum_k \ell(\pi_k H) \leq 1$ then $\ell(H) \leq 1$, which implies $H \leq 1$ because ℓ is increasing and normalized so that $\ell(1) = 1$. If $\pi = e_k$ then $H(e_k) = 1$ is feasible and thus maximal. Conversely, if $H(\pi) = 1$ then the preceding inequality must hold with equality at $H = 1$, which by strict concavity of ℓ requires π to put unit mass on a single coordinate. ■

Lemma 7 (Regularity implied by the learning technology). *Let*

$$\underline{\ell} \equiv \ell'(1) > 0, \quad \bar{\ell} \equiv \ell'(0) < \infty.$$

Under the learning assumptions of Section 3:

(i) *for every $s \in [0, 1]$,*

$$\underline{\ell} s \leq \ell(s) \leq \bar{\ell} s;$$

(ii) *for every $\pi \in \Delta^{K-1}$,*

$$\frac{1}{\bar{\ell}} \leq H(\pi) \leq 1, \quad 1 \leq \lambda(\pi) \leq \bar{\ell};$$

(iii) H is globally Lipschitz on Δ^{K-1} :

$$|H(\pi) - H(\pi')| \leq \frac{\bar{\ell}}{\underline{\ell}} \|\pi - \pi'\|_1;$$

(iv) $\lambda(\pi) = 1/H(\pi)$ is globally Lipschitz on Δ^{K-1} :

$$|\lambda(\pi) - \lambda(\pi')| \leq \frac{\bar{\ell}^3}{\underline{\ell}} \|\pi - \pi'\|_1;$$

(v) Γ is globally Lipschitz on $[0, 1]^K$ under the ℓ_1 -norm. In particular,

$$|\Gamma(z) - \Gamma(z')| \leq \left(\bar{\ell} + 2 \frac{\bar{\ell}^3}{\underline{\ell}} \right) \|z - z'\|_1 \quad \text{for all } z, z' \in [0, 1]^K;$$

(vi)

$$\kappa_\ell > 0.$$

Proof. Because ℓ is concave and continuously differentiable on $[0, 1]$, its derivative is non-increasing there. Hence

$$\underline{\ell} = \ell'(1) \leq \ell'(s) \leq \ell'(0) = \bar{\ell} \quad \text{for all } s \in [0, 1].$$

Integrating from 0 to s gives part (i):

$$\underline{\ell} s \leq \ell(s) \leq \bar{\ell} s.$$

For part (ii), Lemma 6 gives $H(\pi) \leq 1$. On the other hand,

$$1 = \sum_{k=1}^K \ell(H(\pi)\pi_k) \leq \bar{\ell} H(\pi) \sum_{k=1}^K \pi_k = \bar{\ell} H(\pi),$$

so $H(\pi) \geq 1/\bar{\ell}$. The bounds for $\lambda(\pi) = 1/H(\pi)$ follow immediately.

For part (iii), define

$$F(H, \pi) \equiv \sum_{k=1}^K \ell(H\pi_k).$$

By definition, $F(H(\pi), \pi) = 1$ for every π . Let $H = H(\pi)$ and $H' = H(\pi')$. Then

$$|F(H, \pi') - F(H', \pi')| = |F(H, \pi') - F(H, \pi)|.$$

By the mean value theorem in H and the derivative bound from part (i),

$$|F(H, \pi') - F(H', \pi')| \geq \underline{\ell} |H - H'|,$$

because

$$\frac{\partial F}{\partial H}(t, \pi') = \sum_{k=1}^K \pi'_k \ell'(t\pi'_k) \geq \underline{\ell} \sum_{k=1}^K \pi'_k = \underline{\ell}$$

for all $t \in [0, 1]$. By the mean value theorem in each coordinate and the upper derivative bound,

$$|F(H, \pi') - F(H, \pi)| \leq \sum_{k=1}^K \bar{\ell} H |\pi'_k - \pi_k| \leq \bar{\ell} \|\pi - \pi'\|_1,$$

since $H \leq 1$. Combining the two displays yields

$$|H(\pi) - H(\pi')| \leq \frac{\bar{\ell}}{\underline{\ell}} \|\pi - \pi'\|_1.$$

For part (iv),

$$|\lambda(\pi) - \lambda(\pi')| = \left| \frac{1}{H(\pi)} - \frac{1}{H(\pi')} \right| = \frac{|H(\pi) - H(\pi')|}{H(\pi)H(\pi')} \leq \bar{\ell}^2 |H(\pi) - H(\pi')|,$$

and part (iii) implies

$$|\lambda(\pi) - \lambda(\pi')| \leq \frac{\bar{\ell}^3}{\underline{\ell}} \|\pi - \pi'\|_1.$$

For part (v), first note that for any nonzero z ,

$$\Gamma(z) = \|z\|_1 \lambda\left(\frac{z}{\|z\|_1}\right) \leq \bar{\ell} \|z\|_1.$$

So if $z' = 0$ (or symmetrically $z = 0$),

$$|\Gamma(z) - \Gamma(0)| \leq \bar{\ell} \|z\|_1 = \bar{\ell} \|z - z'\|_1.$$

Now suppose $z, z' \neq 0$. Write

$$r = \|z\|_1, \quad r' = \|z'\|_1, \quad \pi = \frac{z}{r}, \quad \pi' = \frac{z'}{r'},$$

and without loss of generality assume $r \geq r'$. Then

$$|\Gamma(z) - \Gamma(z')| = |r\lambda(\pi) - r'\lambda(\pi')| \leq \bar{\ell}|r - r'| + r'|\lambda(\pi) - \lambda(\pi')|.$$

Using part (iv),

$$|\Gamma(z) - \Gamma(z')| \leq \bar{\ell}|r - r'| + \frac{\bar{\ell}^3}{\underline{\ell}} r' \|\pi - \pi'\|_1.$$

Moreover,

$$|r - r'| \leq \|z - z'\|_1,$$

and

$$r' \left\| \frac{z}{r} - \frac{z'}{r'} \right\|_1 = \left\| \frac{r'}{r} z - z' \right\|_1 \leq \left\| \frac{r'}{r} z - z \right\|_1 + \|z - z'\|_1 = (r - r') + \|z - z'\|_1 \leq 2\|z - z'\|_1.$$

Therefore

$$|\Gamma(z) - \Gamma(z')| \leq \left(\bar{\ell} + 2 \frac{\bar{\ell}^3}{\underline{\ell}} \right) \|z - z'\|_1.$$

For part (vi), strict concavity together with $\ell(0) = 0$ and $\ell(1) = 1$ implies

$$\ell'(0) > 1 > \ell'(1).$$

Define

$$\phi(s) \equiv \frac{\ell(s) - s}{s(1-s)} \quad \text{for } s \in (0, 1).$$

Because ℓ is C^1 and $\ell(s) - s = 0$ at $s = 0, 1$, the function ϕ extends continuously to $[0, 1]$ with

$$\phi(0) = \ell'(0) - 1 > 0, \quad \phi(1) = 1 - \ell'(1) > 0.$$

Strict concavity gives $\ell(s) > s$ for $s \in (0, 1)$, so $\phi(s) > 0$ there as well. Hence

$$c_\ell \equiv \min_{s \in [0, 1]} \phi(s) > 0,$$

and therefore

$$\ell(s) \geq s + c_\ell s(1-s) \quad \text{for all } s \in [0, 1].$$

Let $H = H(\pi)$. Then

$$1 = \sum_{k=1}^K \ell(H\pi_k) \geq \sum_{k=1}^K [H\pi_k + c_\ell H\pi_k(1 - H\pi_k)] = H + c_\ell H \left(1 - H \sum_{k=1}^K \pi_k^2 \right).$$

Since $H \leq 1$,

$$1 - H \sum_{k=1}^K \pi_k^2 \geq 1 - \sum_{k=1}^K \pi_k^2 = D(\pi).$$

Thus

$$1 \geq H(1 + c_\ell D(\pi)),$$

or equivalently

$$\lambda(\pi) = \frac{1}{H(\pi)} \geq 1 + c_\ell D(\pi).$$

Hence

$$\kappa_\ell = \inf_{\pi: D(\pi) > 0} \frac{\lambda(\pi) - 1}{D(\pi)} \geq c_\ell > 0.$$

■

The explicit coordination cutoff. Define the primitive coordination cutoff

$$\bar{\theta} \equiv \min \left\{ \frac{\kappa_\ell}{L_\Gamma}, \frac{1}{2L_\Gamma} \right\} > 0. \quad (20)$$

Equation (20) is the cutoff used in Theorem 1.

Lemma 8 (Budget exhaustion for specialists). *Consider a feasible allocation with $H^S > 0$ and let $\bar{\pi} \equiv S/H^S$ denote the aggregate specialist mix. If a positive-measure set of specialists has slack learning budgets, then one can construct another feasible allocation with the same gaps G (hence the same right-hand side of the integration constraint) but strictly higher output. Consequently, in any productive optimum, almost every specialist exhausts the learning budget:*

$$\sum_{k=1}^K \ell(s_{ik}) = 1 \quad \text{for a.e. specialist } i,$$

and thus admits the representation $s_i = H(\pi_i)\pi_i$, where $\pi_i = s_i/\|s_i\|_1$.

Proof. Suppose, towards a contradiction, that there is a set of specialists of positive measure for which $\sum_k \ell(s_{ik}) < 1$. Then there exists $\varepsilon > 0$ and a subset of positive measure such that $\sum_k \ell(s_{ik}) \leq 1 - \varepsilon$ on that subset. Because $\ell(1) = 1$ and ℓ is increasing, feasibility implies $s_{ik} \leq 1$ for all i, k ; hence ℓ is uniformly continuous on $[0, 2]$. Choose $\delta \in (0, 1]$ small enough that

$$\ell(z + \delta) - \ell(z) \leq \varepsilon/K \quad \text{for all } z \in [0, 1].$$

Now add $\delta \bar{\pi}$ to the skill vector of every specialist in the slack-budget subset (leaving all other agents unchanged), i.e. set $s'_i = s_i + \delta \bar{\pi}$ on that subset. The change in learning

cost is at most $\sum_k \varepsilon/K = \varepsilon$, so these specialists remain feasible:

$$\sum_k \ell(s'_{ik}) \leq \sum_k \ell(s_{ik}) + \varepsilon \leq 1.$$

Aggregate specialist knowledge increases by a positive multiple of $\bar{\pi}$, so the aggregate mix remains $\bar{\pi}$. Moreover, for each modified specialist,

$$\|s'_i\|_1 \bar{\pi} - s'_i = (\|s_i\|_1 + \delta)\bar{\pi} - (s_i + \delta \bar{\pi}) = \|s_i\|_1 \bar{\pi} - s_i,$$

so her individual gap vector $\gamma_i = (\|s_i\|_1 \bar{\pi} - s_i)^+$ is unchanged. Therefore G and g are unchanged, so the integration constraint remains satisfied with the same integrator block.

By Lemma 3, every productive optimum has strictly positive output. Since $\bar{\pi}$ is unchanged and

$$Y = VH^S \mathcal{C}(\bar{\pi}, q),$$

we have $\mathcal{C}(\bar{\pi}, q) > 0$. Hence the increase in H^S strictly raises output. This contradicts optimality and proves budget exhaustion. The representation $s_i = H(\pi_i)\pi_i$ then follows directly from the definition of $H(\cdot)$. ■

A.3 A reduced problem conditional on an aggregate mix. By Lemma 8, in any productive optimum we may restrict attention to allocations in which every specialist has the “full” form $s_i = H(\pi_i)\pi_i$. Let $x \equiv \bar{\pi}$ denote the aggregate specialist composition. Define

$$\Delta(\pi, x) \equiv 1 - \mathcal{C}(\pi, x) = \frac{1}{2}\|\pi - x\|_1,$$

where the equality follows from Lemma 1. A specialist of direction π and scale $H(\pi)$ contributes gap vector $H(\pi)(x - \pi)^+$ and gap mass $H(\pi)\Delta(\pi, x)$.

Let μ denote the direction distribution in the specialist population (so μ is a probability measure on Δ^{K-1}). Define the *mastery-weighted* direction distribution

$$\nu(d\pi) \equiv \frac{H(\pi)\mu(d\pi)}{\int H(\tilde{\pi})\mu(d\tilde{\pi})}. \quad (21)$$

Then ν is a probability measure, and its mean equals the aggregate mix: $\mathbb{E}_\nu[\pi] = x$.

For any such ν , define the aggregate gap vector per unit specialist mastery as

$$z_\nu(x) \equiv \mathbb{E}_\nu[(x - \pi)^+] \in \mathbb{R}_+^K. \quad (22)$$

Its total mass is $\|z_\nu(x)\|_1 = \mathbb{E}_\nu[\Delta(\pi, x)]$.

Lemma 9 (Feasibility and reduction via ν). *Suppose specialists are full and let ν be defined by (21). Then*

$$1 = H^S \mathbb{E}_\nu[\lambda(\pi)] + m, \quad G = H^S z_\nu(x), \quad g = H^S \|z_\nu(x)\|_1, \quad Y = V H^S \mathcal{C}(x, q). \quad (23)$$

Moreover, any feasible allocation satisfies

$$H^S \leq \frac{1}{\mathbb{E}_\nu[\lambda(\pi)] + \theta \Gamma(z_\nu(x))}. \quad (24)$$

Equality holds if and only if the integrator block is minimal feasible for the given specialist block, i.e.

$$m = \theta H^S \Gamma(z_\nu(x)).$$

Equivalently, $m = 0$ when $z_\nu(x) = 0$, and if $z_\nu(x) \neq 0$ then $mH(h) = \theta g$ and $s_i = H(h)h$ for almost every integrator, where $h = z_\nu(x)/\|z_\nu(x)\|_1$. Consequently, in any productive optimum,

$$H^S = \frac{1}{\mathbb{E}_\nu[\lambda(\pi)] + \theta \Gamma(z_\nu(x))}, \quad Y = \frac{VC(x, q)}{\mathbb{E}_\nu[\lambda(\pi)] + \theta \Gamma(z_\nu(x))}.$$

Proof. Because specialists are full,

$$S = \int_{i \in \mathcal{S}} s_i di = (1 - m) \int H(\pi) \pi \mu(d\pi), \quad H^S = (1 - m) \int H(\pi) \mu(d\pi).$$

Dividing gives $x = S/H^S = \int \pi \nu(d\pi) = \mathbb{E}_\nu[\pi]$. Next,

$$G = (1 - m) \int H(\pi)(x - \pi)^+ \mu(d\pi) = H^S z_\nu(x),$$

so

$$g = \|G\|_1 = H^S \|z_\nu(x)\|_1.$$

The population identity also implies

$$\mathbb{E}_\nu[\lambda(\pi)] = \int \frac{1}{H(\pi)} \nu(d\pi) = \frac{\int \mu(d\pi)}{\int H(\pi) \mu(d\pi)} = \frac{1}{\int H(\pi) \mu(d\pi)} = \frac{1 - m}{H^S},$$

which proves the first identity in (23). Output equals $VC(S, H^S q) = V H^S \mathcal{C}(x, q)$.

Now turn to feasibility. If $z_\nu(x) = 0$, then $\Gamma(z_\nu(x)) = 0$, so (24) reduces to $1 = H^S \mathbb{E}_\nu[\lambda] + m \geq H^S \mathbb{E}_\nu[\lambda]$, which is immediate. If $z_\nu(x) \neq 0$, then $g > 0$ and the normalized gap profile

is $h = z_\nu(x)/\|z_\nu(x)\|_1$. By Lemma 2, every integrator contributes at most $H(h)$, so total integration capacity satisfies $J \leq mH(h)$. Feasibility $J \geq \theta g$ therefore implies

$$m \geq \theta g/H(h) = \theta H^S \Gamma(z_\nu(x)).$$

Combining this with $1 = H^S \mathbb{E}_\nu[\lambda] + m$ yields (24).

Equality in (24) holds exactly when $m = \theta H^S \Gamma(z_\nu(x))$. If $z_\nu(x) = 0$, this means $m = 0$. If $z_\nu(x) \neq 0$, then equality requires both $mH(h) = \theta g$ and $J = mH(h)$; by Lemma 2, the latter is equivalent to $s_i = H(h)h$ for almost every integrator. Finally, Lemmas 4 and 5 imply that every productive optimum attains equality, which yields the last display. ■

Lemma 9 implies that, conditional on x , maximizing output is equivalent to minimizing

$$\mathbb{E}_\nu[\lambda(\pi)] + \theta \Gamma(z_\nu(x))$$

over mastery-weighted direction distributions ν with mean $\mathbb{E}_\nu[\pi] = x$.

A.4 Shattering into corners. Define the learning-economies index

$$\kappa_\ell \equiv \inf_{\pi \in \Delta^{K-1}: D(\pi) > 0} \frac{\lambda(\pi) - 1}{D(\pi)}. \quad (25)$$

For any non-corner direction realization π , let $E(\pi) \in \{e_1, \dots, e_K\}$ be a random corner with

$$\Pr(E(\pi) = e_k \mid \pi) = \pi_k.$$

This *shattering* transformation preserves the mean because $\mathbb{E}[E(\pi) \mid \pi] = \pi$.

Lemma 10 (Gap expansion under shattering). *Fix a target aggregate composition $x \in \Delta^{K-1}$. For each coordinate j ,*

$$\mathbb{E}\left[(x_j - E_j(\pi))^+ \mid \pi\right] - (x_j - \pi_j)^+ = \min\{\pi_j, x_j\} - \pi_j x_j \geq 0.$$

Summing across coordinates yields

$$\sum_{j=1}^K \left(\mathbb{E}\left[(x_j - E_j(\pi))^+ \mid \pi\right] - (x_j - \pi_j)^+ \right) = \mathcal{C}(\pi, x) - \pi \cdot x \leq D(\pi).$$

Consequently, if ν^c denotes the cornerization of ν , then

$$\|z_{\nu^c}(x) - z_\nu(x)\|_1 \leq \mathbb{E}_\nu[D(\pi)].$$

Moreover,

$$z_{\nu^c}(x) = x \odot (1 - x).$$

Proof. Conditional on π , the random corner $E(\pi)$ equals e_j with probability π_j and is unequal to e_j with probability $1 - \pi_j$. Hence

$$\mathbb{E}[(x_j - E_j(\pi))^+ | \pi] = x_j(1 - \pi_j).$$

If $\pi_j \leq x_j$, the difference from $(x_j - \pi_j)^+ = x_j - \pi_j$ is $\pi_j(1 - x_j)$. If $\pi_j \geq x_j$, the difference from $(x_j - \pi_j)^+ = 0$ is $x_j(1 - \pi_j)$. In either case the difference equals $\min\{\pi_j, x_j\} - \pi_j x_j \geq 0$. Summing over coordinates gives the second display.

Now use the scalar inequality $\min\{a, b\} - ab \leq a(1 - a)$ for $a, b \in [0, 1]$. Applying it coordinatewise with $a = \pi_j$ and $b = x_j$ yields

$$\mathcal{C}(\pi, x) - \pi \cdot x \leq \sum_{j=1}^K \pi_j(1 - \pi_j) = D(\pi).$$

Averaging the coordinatewise identity under ν gives

$$z_{\nu^c}(x) - z_{\nu}(x) = \mathbb{E}_{\nu}[\min\{\pi, x\} - \pi \odot x],$$

so taking ℓ_1 -norms and using nonnegativity yields

$$\|z_{\nu^c}(x) - z_{\nu}(x)\|_1 = \mathbb{E}_{\nu}[\mathcal{C}(\pi, x) - \pi \cdot x] \leq \mathbb{E}_{\nu}[D(\pi)].$$

Finally, since $\mathbb{E}_{\nu}[\pi] = x$,

$$z_{\nu^c, j}(x) = \mathbb{E}_{\nu}[x_j(1 - \pi_j)] = x_j(1 - x_j),$$

which proves $z_{\nu^c}(x) = x \odot (1 - x)$. ■

Proposition 7 (Bang-bang specialization). *Fix any target aggregate composition $x \in \Delta^{K-1}$. If $\theta < \bar{\theta}$, then every optimal allocation is bang-bang: every specialist is a unit-scale corner expert, integrators are efficient in the sense of Lemma 4, and feasibility binds.*

Proof. Fix x and consider the conditional problem described after Lemma 9. Take any feasible mastery-weighted specialist-direction distribution ν with mean x , and let ν^c denote its cornerization.

First, shattering weakly reduces the learning term because $\lambda(e_k) = 1$ for all corners:

$$\mathbb{E}_{\nu^c}[\lambda(\pi)] = 1.$$

Hence

$$\mathbb{E}_\nu[\lambda(\pi)] - \mathbb{E}_{\nu^c}[\lambda(\pi)] = \mathbb{E}_\nu[\lambda(\pi) - 1] \geq \kappa_\ell \mathbb{E}_\nu[D(\pi)].$$

Second, by Lemma 10 and the L_Γ -Lipschitz property of Γ ,

$$\Gamma(z_{\nu^c}(x)) - \Gamma(z_\nu(x)) \leq L_\Gamma \|z_{\nu^c}(x) - z_\nu(x)\|_1 \leq L_\Gamma \mathbb{E}_\nu[D(\pi)].$$

Therefore the conditional objective satisfies

$$\left(\mathbb{E}_\nu[\lambda(\pi)] + \theta \Gamma(z_\nu(x)) \right) - \left(1 + \theta \Gamma(z_{\nu^c}(x)) \right) \geq (\kappa_\ell - \theta L_\Gamma) \mathbb{E}_\nu[D(\pi)].$$

Because $\theta < \bar{\theta} \leq \kappa_\ell / L_\Gamma$, the right-hand side is strictly positive whenever $\mathbb{E}_\nu[D(\pi)] > 0$, i.e. whenever ν assigns positive mass to a non-corner direction. Hence any optimal conditional distribution must satisfy $D(\pi) = 0$ almost surely, so every specialist is a corner expert. Efficient integrators and binding feasibility then follow from Lemmas 4 and 5. ■

Lemma 11 (Reduced-form output, gap vector, and integrator share). *Assume $\theta L_\Gamma < \kappa_\ell$ so that Proposition 7 implies bang-bang specialization. Fix an aggregate specialist mix $x \in \Delta^{K-1}$, and let*

$$O(x) \equiv \mathcal{C}(x, q).$$

In the efficient organization conditional on $\bar{\pi} = x$:

(i) *output is*

$$Y(x) = V \frac{O(x)}{1 + \theta \Gamma(x \odot (1 - x))};$$

(ii) *aggregate coordination burden is*

$$G(x) = (1 - m(x)) x \odot (1 - x), \quad g(x) = (1 - m(x)) D(x);$$

(iii) *the minimal feasible integrator share is*

$$m(x) = \frac{\theta \Gamma(x \odot (1 - x))}{1 + \theta \Gamma(x \odot (1 - x))};$$

(iv) if $D(x) > 0$, the gap profile is

$$h_k(x) = \frac{x_k(1-x_k)}{D(x)}, \quad k = 1, \dots, K.$$

Proof. With unit-scale corner specialists and integrator share m , the specialist share is $1 - m$. Aggregate specialist knowledge is therefore

$$S = (1 - m)x.$$

Since $x, q \in \Delta^{K-1}$, the raw coverage operator satisfies

$$\mathcal{C}(S, \|S\|_1 q) = \mathcal{C}((1 - m)x, (1 - m)q) = (1 - m)\mathcal{C}(x, q) = (1 - m)O(x),$$

which proves the output formula once $m(x)$ is characterized.

Now fix a specialist assigned to domain k . Her knowledge stock is e_k , while the organizational mix is x . The individual gap vector is

$$\gamma^{(k)} = (x - e_k)^+.$$

Its j th coordinate equals x_j for $j \neq k$ and zero otherwise. Averaging across specialist assignments in proportions x_k gives aggregate gap vector

$$G = (1 - m) \sum_{k=1}^K x_k \gamma^{(k)} = (1 - m)x \odot (1 - x),$$

which proves the formula for $G(x)$. Summing coordinates yields

$$g = (1 - m) \sum_{k=1}^K x_k(1 - x_k) = (1 - m)D(x).$$

If $D(x) > 0$, normalizing by total gap mass gives

$$h_k(x) = \frac{x_k(1 - x_k)}{D(x)}.$$

Finally, a gap-matched integrator supplies $H(h(x))$ units of effective coordination capacity, so aggregate capacity is $J = mH(h(x))$. Binding feasibility therefore gives

$$mH(h(x)) = \theta(1 - m)D(x).$$

Equivalently,

$$m = \theta(1 - m) \frac{D(x)}{H(h(x))} = \theta(1 - m) \Gamma(x \odot (1 - x)),$$

which solves to

$$m(x) = \frac{\theta \Gamma(x \odot (1 - x))}{1 + \theta \Gamma(x \odot (1 - x))}.$$

Substituting

$$1 - m(x) = \frac{1}{1 + \theta \Gamma(x \odot (1 - x))}$$

into the output formula gives

$$Y(x) = V \frac{O(x)}{1 + \theta \Gamma(x \odot (1 - x))}.$$

■

Lemma 12 (Lipschitz control of the reduced-form coordination term). *The map*

$$x \mapsto \Gamma(x \odot (1 - x))$$

is Lipschitz on Δ^{K-1} with constant L_Γ :

$$|\Gamma(x \odot (1 - x)) - \Gamma(y \odot (1 - y))| \leq L_\Gamma \|x - y\|_1 \quad \text{for all } x, y \in \Delta^{K-1}.$$

Consequently,

$$|\Gamma(x \odot (1 - x)) - \Gamma(q \odot (1 - q))| \leq 2L_\Gamma (1 - \mathcal{C}(x, q)).$$

Proof. For each coordinate, the map $\phi(t) = t(1 - t)$ satisfies $|\phi'(t)| = |1 - 2t| \leq 1$ on $[0, 1]$. Hence

$$\|x \odot (1 - x) - y \odot (1 - y)\|_1 \leq \|x - y\|_1.$$

Applying the L_Γ -Lipschitz property of Γ gives the first display. The second then follows from Lemma 1, which implies $\|x - q\|_1 = 2(1 - \mathcal{C}(x, q))$. ■

Proposition 8 (Productive optimum). *If $\theta < \bar{\theta}$, then $x = q$ uniquely maximizes $Y(x)$ over Δ^{K-1} . Consequently:*

$$h_k^* = \frac{q_k(1 - q_k)}{D(q)}, \quad m^*(q) = \frac{\theta D(q)}{H(h^*) + \theta D(q)}, \quad Y^*(q) = \frac{VH(h^*)}{H(h^*) + \theta D(q)}.$$

Proof. By Lemma 11,

$$Y(q) - Y(x) = V \left[\frac{1}{1 + \theta \Gamma(q \odot (1 - q))} - \frac{O(x)}{1 + \theta \Gamma(x \odot (1 - x))} \right].$$

Let $t(x) \equiv 1 - O(x)$. Since denominators are positive, this has the same sign as

$$\left(1 + \theta \Gamma(x \odot (1 - x))\right) - O(x) \left(1 + \theta \Gamma(q \odot (1 - q))\right)$$

that is,

$$t(x) + \theta \left(\Gamma(x \odot (1 - x)) - \Gamma(q \odot (1 - q)) + t(x) \Gamma(q \odot (1 - q)) \right).$$

By Lemma 12,

$$\Gamma(x \odot (1 - x)) - \Gamma(q \odot (1 - q)) \geq -2L_\Gamma t(x).$$

Therefore

$$\left(1 + \theta \Gamma(x \odot (1 - x))\right) - O(x) \left(1 + \theta \Gamma(q \odot (1 - q))\right) \geq t(x) \left[1 - 2\theta L_\Gamma\right].$$

Because $\theta < \bar{\theta} \leq 1/(2L_\Gamma)$, the bracket is strictly positive. Thus $Y(q) - Y(x) \geq 0$, with strict inequality whenever $t(x) > 0$. Since $t(x) = 0$ if and only if $O(x) = 1$, and $O(x) = 1$ if and only if $x = q$, the maximizer is unique. The formulas for h , $m^*(q)$, and $Y^*(q)$ then follow from Lemma 11 evaluated at $x = q$. ■

Proof of Theorem 1. Proposition 7 implies that, conditional on any aggregate specialist mix x , every optimal organization is bang-bang, with efficient integrators and binding feasibility. Lemma 11 then delivers the reduced-form mapping from x to $(Y(x), m(x), h(x))$. Finally, Proposition 8 shows that $x = q$ uniquely maximizes $Y(x)$, and provides the formulas for h^* , m^* , and Y^* . At the productive optimum,

$$m^* = \frac{\theta D(q)}{H(h^*) + \theta D(q)} = \frac{\theta \Gamma(q \odot (1 - q))}{1 + \theta \Gamma(q \odot (1 - q))}.$$

Because Γ is L_Γ -Lipschitz on $[0, 1]^K$ and $\Gamma(0) = 0$,

$$\Gamma(q \odot (1 - q)) \leq L_\Gamma \|q \odot (1 - q)\|_1 = L_\Gamma D(q).$$

Since $\theta < 1/(2L_\Gamma)$,

$$\theta \Gamma(q \odot (1 - q)) < \frac{D(q)}{2},$$

and since $q \in \Delta^{K-1}$,

$$D(q) = 1 - \sum_{k=1}^K q_k^2 \leq 1 - \frac{1}{K}.$$

Therefore

$$m^* < \frac{(1 - 1/K)/2}{1 + (1 - 1/K)/2} = \frac{K - 1}{3K - 1} < \frac{1}{3}.$$

Combining these steps yields the three claims in Theorem 1. ■

Proof of Proposition 1. At the productive allocation, each specialist is a corner expert, so average specialist system knowledge is

$$B_S^q = \sum_{k=1}^K q_k \mathcal{C}(e_k, u) = q \cdot u \leq u_{(K)}.$$

Also,

$$B_M^q = H(h^*(q))^p \mathcal{C}(h^*(q), u).$$

For the scale term, let $H^* \equiv H(h^*(q))$. Since $\sum_k h_k^*(q) = 1$, Jensen's inequality gives

$$\frac{1}{K} \sum_{k=1}^K \ell(H^* h_k^*(q)) \leq \ell\left(\frac{H^*}{K}\right).$$

Because $\sum_k \ell(H^* h_k^*(q)) = 1$, the left-hand side equals $1/K$. Hence

$$\ell\left(\frac{H^*}{K}\right) \geq \frac{1}{K},$$

and monotonicity of ℓ implies

$$H(h^*(q)) = H^* \geq K \ell^{-1}(1/K).$$

For the coverage term, note that

$$h_k^*(q) = \frac{q_k(1 - q_k)}{D(q)} \leq \frac{1}{2} \quad \text{for every } k,$$

because

$$D(q) = \sum_{j=1}^K q_j(1 - q_j) \geq q_k(1 - q_k) + \sum_{j \neq k} q_j q_k = 2q_k(1 - q_k).$$

Hence $h^*(q)$ belongs to the polytope

$$\mathcal{H} \equiv \{h \in \Delta^{K-1} : h_k \leq 1/2 \forall k\}.$$

The map $h \mapsto \mathcal{C}(h, u) = \sum_k \min\{h_k, u_k\}$ is concave in h , so its minimum over the convex set \mathcal{H} is attained at an extreme point. The extreme points of \mathcal{H} are vectors of the form

$$\frac{1}{2}e_a + \frac{1}{2}e_b, \quad a \neq b.$$

For such a vector,

$$\mathcal{C}\left(\frac{1}{2}e_a + \frac{1}{2}e_b, u\right) = \min\{1/2, u_a\} + \min\{1/2, u_b\}.$$

Because $K \geq 3$ and $u \in \text{int } \Delta^{K-1}$, at most one coordinate of u can exceed $1/2$. Therefore the two smallest elements of $\{\min(1/2, u_k)\}_{k=1}^K$ are $u_{(1)}$ and $u_{(2)}$, so every extreme point satisfies

$$\mathcal{C}\left(\frac{1}{2}e_a + \frac{1}{2}e_b, u\right) \geq u_{(1)} + u_{(2)}.$$

It follows that

$$\mathcal{C}(h^*(q), u) \geq u_{(1)} + u_{(2)}.$$

Therefore

$$B_M^q \geq \left(K \ell^{-1}(1/K)\right)^P [u_{(1)} + u_{(2)}].$$

Under Assumption 1,

$$\left(K \ell^{-1}(1/K)\right)^P [u_{(1)} + u_{(2)}] > u_{(K)} \geq B_S^q.$$

Hence

$$B_M^q > B_S^q. \quad \blacksquare$$

B Political equilibrium

For any platform (e, z) , group-specific deterministic utility is

$$U_S(e, z) = y_S + \log\left(\frac{(1-z)\mathcal{G}(e, Y)}{1-m}\right), \quad U_M(e, z) = y_M + \log\left(\frac{z\mathcal{G}(e, Y)}{m}\right).$$

Lemma 13 (Governance choice). *Under Assumption 2, for every $Y > 0$ and $B > 0$, problem*

$$e^*(Y, B) \in \arg \max_{e \geq 0} \{B \log \mathcal{G}(e, Y) - 4\Lambda_0 c(e)\}, \quad (26)$$

has a unique interior solution $e^(Y, B)$. Moreover,*

$$e_B^*(Y, B) > 0, \quad \mathcal{R}_B(Y, B) > 0.$$

Proof. Define

$$\Psi(e; Y, B) \equiv B \log \mathcal{G}(e, Y) - 4\Lambda_0 c(e).$$

By Assumption 2, $\Psi(\cdot; Y, B)$ is strictly concave on \mathbb{R}_+ . Its derivative is

$$\Psi_e(e; Y, B) = B \partial_e \log \mathcal{G}(e, Y) - 4\Lambda_0 c'(e).$$

The Inada condition on $\partial_e \log \mathcal{G}(e, Y)$ and the normalization $c'(0) = 0$ imply

$$\lim_{e \downarrow 0} \Psi_e(e; Y, B) = +\infty,$$

while $\lim_{e \rightarrow \infty} \partial_e \log \mathcal{G}(e, Y) = 0$ and $\lim_{e \rightarrow \infty} c'(e) = +\infty$ imply

$$\lim_{e \rightarrow \infty} \Psi_e(e; Y, B) = -\infty.$$

Therefore Ψ has a unique maximizer, and it is interior. This proves existence and uniqueness of $e^*(Y, B)$.

Let

$$F(e, Y, B) \equiv B \partial_e \log \mathcal{G}(e, Y) - 4\Lambda_0 c'(e).$$

At $e = e^*(Y, B)$, the first-order condition is $F(e^*(Y, B), Y, B) = 0$. By strict concavity,

$$F_e(e^*(Y, B), Y, B) = B \partial_{ee} \log \mathcal{G}(e^*(Y, B), Y) - 4\Lambda_0 c''(e^*(Y, B)) < 0.$$

The implicit-function theorem therefore applies. Since

$$F_B(e^*(Y, B), Y, B) = \partial_e \log \mathcal{G}(e^*(Y, B), Y) > 0,$$

we have

$$e_B^*(Y, B) = -\frac{F_B}{F_e} > 0.$$

Finally, since $\mathcal{R}(Y, B) = \mathcal{G}(e^*(Y, B), Y)$,

$$\mathcal{R}_B(Y, B) = \mathcal{G}_e(e^*(Y, B), Y)e_B^*(Y, B) > 0.$$

■

Proof of Proposition 2. Since every feasible knowledge profile satisfies $\|s_i\|_1 \leq 1$, we have $B_i \leq \|s_i\|_1^p \leq 1$. Equality would require both $\|s_i\|_1 = 1$ and $\mathcal{C}(\pi_i, u) = 1$, hence $\pi_i = u$, which is impossible because $u \in \text{int}\Delta^{K-1}$ implies $H(u) < 1$. Thus $B_i < 1$ for every citizen, and therefore the group averages satisfy $B_g < 1$. Define

$$\beta_g \equiv \frac{B_g}{\Lambda_0} \in (0, 1), \quad g \in \{S, M\}.$$

Fix candidate R 's platform (\bar{e}, \bar{z}) , and let

$$\bar{t}_S \equiv t_S(\bar{e}, \bar{z}), \quad \bar{t}_M \equiv t_M(\bar{e}, \bar{z}).$$

By (13)–(14), the probability that a voter in group $g \in \{S, M\}$ votes for candidate L is

$$\Psi_g(t_g; \bar{t}_g) \equiv \frac{\exp(U_g^L/\Lambda_g)}{\exp(U_g^L/\Lambda_g) + \exp(U_g^R/\Lambda_g)} = \frac{t_g^{\beta_g}}{t_g^{\beta_g} + \bar{t}_g^{\beta_g}},$$

where $\Lambda_g = \Lambda_0/B_g$. Extend Ψ_g continuously to $t_g = 0$ by $\Psi_g(0; \bar{t}_g) = 0$.

Hence candidate L 's exact best-response problem is equivalently

$$\max_{e \geq 0, t_S, t_M \geq 0} (1-m)\Psi_S(t_S; \bar{t}_S) + m\Psi_M(t_M; \bar{t}_M) - c(e)$$

subject to

$$(1-m)t_S + mt_M \leq \mathcal{G}(e, Y).$$

Indeed, any platform (e, z) induces (t_S, t_M) , and conversely any feasible (e, t_S, t_M) with equality can be implemented by

$$z = \frac{mt_M}{\mathcal{G}(e, Y)}.$$

Since each Ψ_g is strictly increasing in t_g , the constraint binds at an optimum.

For $g \in \{S, M\}$,

$$\Psi_g'(t; \bar{t}_g) = \frac{\beta_g \bar{t}_g^{\beta_g} t^{\beta_g - 1}}{(t^{\beta_g} + \bar{t}_g^{\beta_g})^2},$$

and

$$\Psi_g''(t; \bar{t}_g) = \frac{\beta_g \bar{t}_g^{\beta_g} t^{\beta_g-2} \left[(\beta_g - 1) \bar{t}_g^{\beta_g} - (\beta_g + 1) t^{\beta_g} \right]}{(t^{\beta_g} + \bar{t}_g^{\beta_g})^3} < 0,$$

because $0 < \beta_g \leq 1$. Thus each $\Psi_g(\cdot; \bar{t}_g)$ is strictly concave. Since c is strictly convex, $-c(e)$ is strictly concave; and because, by the maintained assumptions on \mathcal{G} , the map $e \mapsto \mathcal{G}(e, Y)$ is concave, the feasible set

$$\left\{ (t_S, t_M, e) \in \mathbb{R}_+^3 : (1-m)t_S + mt_M \leq \mathcal{G}(e, Y) \right\}$$

is convex. Hence the objective is strictly concave on a convex feasible set.

Moreover, each Ψ_g is bounded above by 1, while $c(e) \rightarrow \infty$ as $e \rightarrow \infty$. Therefore, the objective is coercive in e , so there exists $\bar{e} < \infty$ such that every maximizer satisfies $e \leq \bar{e}$. On $[0, \bar{e}]$, feasibility implies that t_S and t_M are bounded as well, so the feasible set can be restricted to a compact subset of \mathbb{R}_+^3 . By continuity, an exact best response exists; by strict concavity, it is unique.

Now consider a symmetric profile, so that $\bar{t}_g = t_g$. The KKT conditions for the unique best response are

$$\Psi_S'(t_S; t_S) = \mu, \quad \Psi_M'(t_M; t_M) = \mu, \quad \mu \mathcal{G}_e(e, Y) = c'(e),$$

together with

$$(1-m)t_S + mt_M = \mathcal{G}(e, Y).$$

Since

$$\Psi_g'(t_g; t_g) = \frac{\beta_g}{4t_g},$$

the first two conditions imply

$$\frac{\beta_S}{4t_S} = \frac{\beta_M}{4t_M} \implies \frac{t_M}{t_S} = \frac{\beta_M}{\beta_S} = \frac{B_M}{B_S}.$$

Using the binding resource constraint and $B_{soc} = (1-m)B_S + mB_M$, we obtain

$$t_g^{pol} = \frac{B_g}{B_{soc}} \mathcal{G}(e, Y), \quad g \in \{S, M\},$$

and therefore

$$z^{pol} = \frac{mt_M^{pol}}{\mathcal{G}(e, Y)} = \frac{mB_M}{B_{soc}}.$$

Moreover,

$$\mu = \frac{\beta_S}{4t_S^{pol}} = \frac{B_{soc}}{4\Lambda_0\mathcal{G}(e, Y)}.$$

Substituting into the first-order condition with respect to e yields

$$B_{soc} \partial_e \log \mathcal{G}(e, Y) = 4\Lambda_0 c'(e).$$

By Lemma 13, this equation has the unique solution

$$e^{pol} = e^*(Y, B_{soc}).$$

Hence the platform

$$(e^{pol}, z^{pol}) = \left(e^*(Y, B_{soc}), \frac{mB_M}{B_{soc}} \right)$$

satisfies the KKT system for candidate L 's exact best-response problem against itself. By strict concavity, it is the unique best response to itself, and therefore a symmetric equilibrium. To rule out asymmetric pure equilibria, let (e^L, t_S^L, t_M^L) and (e^R, t_S^R, t_M^R) be any pure-strategy equilibrium in the service formulation. Since $0 < \beta_g < 1$, no equilibrium can have $t_g^a = 0$: if $t_g^{-a} > 0$, then $\Psi'_g(t; t_g^{-a}) \rightarrow +\infty$ as $t \downarrow 0$; if $t_g^{-a} = 0$, then candidate a can secure group g 's votes with an arbitrarily small positive transfer. The Inada condition and $c'(0) = 0$ likewise rule out $e^a = 0$. Hence the interior KKT conditions apply to both candidates, so there exist multipliers $\mu_L, \mu_R > 0$ such that

$$\Psi'_g(t_g^L; t_g^R) = \mu_L, \quad \Psi'_g(t_g^R; t_g^L) = \mu_R, \quad g \in \{S, M\},$$

$$\mu_L \mathcal{G}_e(e^L, Y) = c'(e^L), \quad \mu_R \mathcal{G}_e(e^R, Y) = c'(e^R),$$

and

$$(1 - m)t_S^a + mt_M^a = \mathcal{G}(e^a, Y), \quad a \in \{L, R\}.$$

Now

$$t \Psi'_g(t; \bar{t}) = \frac{\beta_g t^{\beta_g} \bar{t}^{\beta_g}}{(t^{\beta_g} + \bar{t}^{\beta_g})^2} = \bar{t} \Psi'_g(\bar{t}; t),$$

so at equilibrium

$$\mu_L t_g^L = \mu_R t_g^R, \quad g \in \{S, M\}.$$

Multiplying the resource constraints by μ_L and μ_R , respectively, and using the previous

identity for both groups yields

$$\mu_L \mathcal{G}(e^L, Y) = \mu_R \mathcal{G}(e^R, Y).$$

Combining this with the first-order conditions in e gives

$$\frac{c'(e^L)}{\partial_e \log \mathcal{G}(e^L, Y)} = \frac{c'(e^R)}{\partial_e \log \mathcal{G}(e^R, Y)}.$$

Under Assumption 2, the map

$$e \mapsto \frac{c'(e)}{\partial_e \log \mathcal{G}(e, Y)}$$

is strictly increasing, because c' is strictly increasing while $\partial_e \log \mathcal{G}(e, Y)$ is positive and strictly decreasing. Therefore $e^L = e^R$. The first-order conditions in e then imply $\mu_L = \mu_R$, and hence

$$t_S^L = t_S^R, \quad t_M^L = t_M^R.$$

Thus every pure-strategy equilibrium is symmetric. Since the symmetric KKT system solved above has a unique solution, the platform

$$(e^{pol}, z^{pol}) = \left(e^*(Y, B_{soc}), \frac{mB_M}{B_{soc}} \right)$$

is the unique pure-strategy equilibrium.

Finally, writing

$$\mathcal{R}(Y, B_{soc}) \equiv \mathcal{G}(e^{pol}, Y),$$

we obtain

$$t_g^{pol} = \frac{B_g}{B_{soc}} \mathcal{R}(Y, B_{soc}),$$

which is (15). The comparative statics $e_B^*(Y, B_{soc}) > 0$ and $\mathcal{R}_B(Y, B_{soc}) > 0$ follow from Lemma 13. If $B_M > B_S$, then $z^{pol} > m$ and $t_M^{pol} > t_S^{pol}$. ■

Proof of Proposition 3. Substitute (15) into

$$\mathcal{V}(\mathcal{A}) = (1 - m(\mathcal{A})) \log t_S^{pol}(\mathcal{A}) + m(\mathcal{A}) \log t_M^{pol}(\mathcal{A}).$$

Equation (17) is algebraic. Nonnegativity of $\mathcal{D}(\mathcal{A})$ follows from concavity of \log :

$$(1 - m) \log B_S + m \log B_M \leq \log((1 - m)B_S + mB_M) = \log B^{soc}.$$

Equality holds if and only if $B_S = B_M$. ■

Proof of Remark 1. Fix production output Y . Proposition 3 implies

$$\mathcal{V} = \log \mathcal{R}(Y, B^{soc}) - \mathcal{D}.$$

Since $\mathcal{R}_B(Y, B^{soc}) > 0$, ex post service welfare is increasing in B^{soc} . Since $\mathcal{D} \geq 0$, it is maximized by minimizing dispersion, which requires $B_S = B_M$. Under the feasible set $[0, B^{\max}(u)]^2$, the planner therefore chooses

$$B_S = B_M = B^{\max}(u).$$

Equation (15) then gives $z^{util} = m$ and $t_S^{util} = t_M^{util}$. ■

C Competitive implementation

This section proves Theorem 2. I use a posted-job interpretation of the competitive equilibrium. A firm chooses a menu of specialist and integrator jobs and a scale of operation. A specialist job of direction π requires the profile $H(\pi)\pi$; an integrator job for gap bundle h requires the profile $H(h)h$. Workers may choose any feasible skill profile before entering the labor market, but only the profiles attached to profit-maximizing jobs are rewarded at the equilibrium role wages. Profiles that are not in demand are not paid for by the market. For convenience, I represent the menu of active jobs by the induced design (x, ν) .

Let w_g denote the net wage received in role $g \in \{S, M\}$, and define

$$\tilde{V} \equiv (1 - \tau)V.$$

Since multiplying firm profits by the positive constant $1 - \tau$ does not change the unit-cost problem, the decentralization argument can be carried out entirely in (w_S, w_M, \tilde{V}) units.

If a firm operates design (x, ν) at scale a , the implied specialist-job measure is

$$N_S(d\pi) = a \lambda(\pi) \nu(d\pi),$$

so that total specialist mastery equals

$$\int H(\pi) N_S(d\pi) = a.$$

The implied integrator employment is the minimal feasible mass

$$a\theta\Gamma(z_\nu(x)).$$

This is exactly the labor-requirement mapping in (27), so the unit-cost problem is unchanged.

Firm problem. Fix a firm. A design is a pair (x, ν) , where $x \in \Delta^{K-1}$ is the aggregate specialist mix and ν is a mastery-weighted distribution of specialist directions with mean x . If the firm operates at scale $a \geq 0$, measured in units of specialist mastery, then the cost-minimizing implementation of (x, ν) uses full specialists and the minimal feasible integrator layer. By Lemma 9,

$$n_S(a, \nu) = a\mathbb{E}_\nu[\lambda(\pi)], \quad n_M(a, x, \nu) = a\theta\Gamma(z_\nu(x)), \quad y(a, x, \nu) = aVC(x, q). \quad (27)$$

Hence, at role wages (w_S, w_M) ,

$$\pi(a, x, \nu; w_S, w_M) = a\left[VC(x, q) - \frac{w_S}{1-\tau}\mathbb{E}_\nu[\lambda(\pi)] - \theta\frac{w_M}{1-\tau}\Gamma(z_\nu(x))\right]. \quad (28)$$

Because (28) is linear in scale, active firms choose designs minimizing unit cost. Writing

$$r \equiv \frac{w_M}{w_S},$$

this is equivalent to minimizing

$$c(x, \nu; r) = \frac{\mathbb{E}_\nu[\lambda(\pi)] + \theta r\Gamma(z_\nu(x))}{C(x, q)}. \quad (29)$$

Lemma 14 (Private bang-bang). *Fix $r \geq 0$. If*

$$\theta r < \frac{\kappa_\ell}{L_\Gamma},$$

then, for every aggregate specialist mix $x \in \Delta^{K-1}$, the unit-cost problem (29) is uniquely minimized by corner specialists.

Proof. Fix x . Since $C(x, q)$ is constant in ν , minimizing (29) is equivalent to minimizing

$$\mathbb{E}_\nu[\lambda(\pi)] + \theta r\Gamma(z_\nu(x)).$$

The proof of Proposition 7 applies verbatim with θ replaced by θr . Since $\theta r < \kappa_\ell/L_\Gamma$, cornerization strictly lowers the objective unless specialists are already corners. ■

Lemma 15 (Private alignment). *Fix $r \geq 0$. If*

$$\theta r < \frac{1}{2L_\Gamma},$$

then, among corner-specialist designs, unit cost is uniquely minimized at $x = q$.

Proof. Under bang-bang specialization, Lemma 11 implies

$$c(x; r) = \frac{1 + \theta r \Gamma(x \odot (1 - x))}{VC(x, q)}.$$

The proof of Proposition 8 applies verbatim with θ replaced by θr . Since $\theta r < 1/(2L_\Gamma)$, the unique minimizer is $x = q$. ■

Lemma 16 (Primitive bound on interior wage ratios). *Let*

$$q_{(1)} \equiv \min_k q_k, \quad \underline{B} \equiv \bar{\ell}^{-p} u_{(1)}, \quad \bar{\Delta} \equiv \log(1/\underline{B}).$$

If \mathcal{A} is an interior competitive equilibrium and

$$\theta < \frac{\tilde{V} q_{(1)}}{2\bar{\ell}\bar{\Delta}},$$

then its equilibrium wage ratio satisfies

$$\frac{w_M}{w_S} \leq \bar{r} \equiv \frac{2(\tilde{V} + \bar{\ell}\bar{\Delta})}{\tilde{V} q_{(1)}}.$$

Proof. Let (x, ν) denote the design of any active firm and write

$$C \equiv \mathcal{C}(x, q), \quad E \equiv \mathbb{E}_\nu[\lambda(\pi)], \quad A \equiv \Gamma(z_\nu(x)).$$

Worker indifference in an interior equilibrium implies

$$w_S - w_M = \Delta(\mathcal{A}), \quad \Delta(\mathcal{A}) \equiv \log\left(\frac{B_M(\mathcal{A})}{B_S(\mathcal{A})}\right).$$

Zero profits imply

$$\tilde{V}C = w_S E + \theta w_M A.$$

Solving for the wage ratio gives

$$\frac{w_M}{w_S} = \frac{\tilde{V}C - E\Delta(\mathcal{A})}{\tilde{V}C + \theta A \Delta(\mathcal{A})} \leq \frac{\tilde{V}C + E|\Delta(\mathcal{A})|}{\tilde{V}C - \theta A |\Delta(\mathcal{A})|}.$$

Now $C \geq q_{(1)}$ and $C \leq 1$. Also $E \leq \bar{\ell}$ and $A \leq \bar{\ell}$. Finally, every full knowledge profile satisfies

$$B \geq \bar{\ell}^{-p} u_{(1)} = \underline{B},$$

so any interior allocation satisfies

$$|\Delta(\mathcal{A})| \leq \bar{\Delta}.$$

Therefore

$$\frac{w_M}{w_S} \leq \frac{\tilde{V} + \bar{\ell} \bar{\Delta}}{\tilde{V} q_{(1)} - \theta \bar{\ell} \bar{\Delta}}.$$

Under

$$\theta < \frac{\tilde{V} q_{(1)}}{2 \bar{\ell} \bar{\Delta}},$$

the denominator is at least $\frac{\tilde{V} q_{(1)}}{2}$, and hence

$$\frac{w_M}{w_S} \leq \frac{2(\tilde{V} + \bar{\ell} \bar{\Delta})}{\tilde{V} q_{(1)}} = \bar{r}.$$

■

Proof of Theorem 2. At the productive allocation \mathcal{A}^q ,

$$\Delta^q = V_M(\mathcal{A}^q) - V_S(\mathcal{A}^q) = \log\left(\frac{B_M^q}{B_S^q}\right),$$

where the equality uses (15). Let

$$\beta \equiv \theta \frac{D(q)}{H(h^*)}.$$

Solving

$$w_S + \beta w_M = \tilde{V}, \quad w_S - w_M = \Delta^q,$$

gives

$$w_M = \frac{\tilde{V} - \Delta^q}{1 + \beta}, \quad w_S = \frac{\tilde{V} + \beta \Delta^q}{1 + \beta}.$$

Because $\Delta^q < \tilde{V}$, both wages are strictly positive. Moreover $w_M/w_S < 1$, so

$$\theta \frac{w_M}{w_S} < \theta < \bar{\theta}.$$

By Lemmas 14 and 15, the productive design is privately cost-minimizing at those wages. Zero profits hold because $w_S + \beta w_M = \tilde{V}$, and workers are indifferent across the active specialist and integrator jobs because $w_S - w_M = \Delta^q$. Jobs based on other profiles are not active in equilibrium because they imply higher unit cost and therefore can support only weakly lower wages. Let active firms use the design \mathcal{A}^q , and choose total scale so that labor markets clear. This proves interior support.

Now let \mathcal{A} be any interior competitive equilibrium. By Lemma 16,

$$\frac{w_M}{w_S} \leq \bar{r}.$$

Under $\theta < \frac{\bar{\theta}}{\bar{r}}$, it follows that $\theta \frac{w_M}{w_S} < \bar{\theta}$. Applying Lemmas 14 and 15, every active firm must therefore choose the productive design. Hence the induced aggregate allocation is \mathcal{A}^q . This proves uniqueness among interior competitive equilibria. ■

D Welfare decomposition and excess specialization

Proof of Proposition 4. Along a differentiable family of interior feasible allocations,

$$\mathcal{W}_b = (1 - \tau)Y_b + \log \mathcal{R}(Y_b, B_b^{\text{soc}}) - \mathcal{D}_b.$$

Differentiating gives (18). ■

Lemma 17 (Broadening and aggregate civic capacity). *Along the broadening family $\{\mathcal{A}(b)\}_{b \in [0,1]}$, broadened specialists keep direction q , so the aggregate specialist mix remains q and the gap profile remains $h^\star(q)$. Hence*

$$m(b) = \frac{\theta(1-b)D(q)}{H(h^\star(q)) + \theta(1-b)D(q)}.$$

Moreover,

$$B^{\text{soc}}(b) = (1 - m(b)) \left[(1 - b)q \cdot u + b H(q)^p C(q, u) \right] + m(b) B_M^q,$$

where

$$B_M^q \equiv H(h^\star(q))^p C(h^\star(q), u).$$

Writing

$$m^q(\theta) \equiv m(0) = \frac{\theta D(q)}{H(h^*(q)) + \theta D(q)},$$

it follows that

$$\left. \frac{dB^{soc}(b)}{db} \right|_{b=0} = (1 - m^q(\theta)) \left[H(q)^p C(q, u) - B^{soc}(0) \right].$$

Consequently, if

$$H(q)^p C(q, u) > q \cdot u,$$

then

$$\left. \frac{dB^{soc}(b)}{db} \right|_{b=0} > 0$$

for all sufficiently small θ .

More explicitly, if

$$q \cdot u < H(q)^p C(q, u) < B_M^q,$$

then

$$\left. \frac{dB^{soc}(b)}{db} \right|_{b=0} > 0 \iff \theta < \bar{\theta}(q, u),$$

where

$$\bar{\theta}(q, u) = \frac{H(h^*(q)) \left[H(q)^p C(q, u) - q \cdot u \right]}{D(q) \left[B_M^q - H(q)^p C(q, u) \right]}.$$

If $H(q)^p C(q, u) \geq B_M^q$, the derivative is positive for every $\theta > 0$.

Proof. A broadened specialist has profile $H(q)q$, so

$$\|H(q)q\|_1 q - H(q)q = 0.$$

Hence broadened specialists generate no coordination gaps. Only the remaining corner specialists contribute to fragmentation, which gives the expression for $m(b)$.

The expression for $B^{soc}(b)$ is immediate: among specialists, a share $1 - b$ have system knowledge $q \cdot u$ and a share b have system knowledge $H(q)^p C(q, u)$, while integrators retain system knowledge B_M^q .

Differentiating at $b = 0$, and using

$$m'(0) = -m^q(\theta) (1 - m^q(\theta)),$$

gives

$$\left. \frac{dB^{soc}(b)}{db} \right|_{b=0} = (1 - m^q(\theta)) \left[H(q)^p C(q, u) - B^{soc}(0) \right].$$

Since

$$B^{soc}(0) = q \cdot u + m^q(\theta)(B_M^q - q \cdot u)$$

and $m^q(\theta) \rightarrow 0$ as $\theta \downarrow 0$, the small- θ claim follows immediately from

$$H(q)^p C(q, u) > q \cdot u.$$

Solving

$$H(q)^p C(q, u) > q \cdot u + m^q(\theta)(B_M^q - q \cdot u)$$

for θ yields the explicit cutoff $\bar{\theta}(q, u)$. ■

Proof of Theorem 3. By Lemma 17,

$$\left. \frac{dB^{soc}(b)}{db} \right|_{b=0} > 0$$

for all sufficiently small θ .

Evaluating Proposition 4 at $b = 0$,

$$\mathcal{W}'(0) = \left[(1 - \tau) + \frac{\mathcal{R}_Y(Y(0), B^{soc}(0))}{\mathcal{R}(Y(0), B^{soc}(0))} \right] Y'(0) + \frac{\mathcal{R}_B(Y(0), B^{soc}(0))}{\mathcal{R}(Y(0), B^{soc}(0))} \left. \frac{dB^{soc}(b)}{db} \right|_{b=0} - \mathcal{D}'(0).$$

Because $\left. \frac{dB^{soc}(b)}{db} \right|_{b=0} > 0$, the governance term is strictly positive and linear in $\frac{\mathcal{R}_B(Y(0), B^{soc}(0))}{\mathcal{R}(Y(0), B^{soc}(0))}$. Hence, for sufficiently large $\mathcal{R}_B(Y(0), B^{soc}(0))/\mathcal{R}(Y(0), B^{soc}(0))$,

$$\mathcal{W}'(0) > 0. \quad \blacksquare$$

Remark 2. *This proof makes clear why a small occupational-rent wedge does not imply small democratic losses. Theorem 2 controls only the continuation-value term relevant for occupational sorting. Theorem 3, by contrast, is driven by the full derivative of welfare and in particular by the governance term*

$$\frac{\mathcal{R}_B(Y(0), B^{soc}(0))}{\mathcal{R}(Y(0), B^{soc}(0))} \left. \frac{dB^{soc}(b)}{db} \right|_{b=0},$$

which can be large whenever effective public resources are highly sensitive to civic capacity.

E Comparative Statics

This section proves the comparative-statics results reported in the main text.

Proof of Proposition 5. Write $h \equiv h^*(q)$ and

$$m^q(\theta) \equiv \frac{\theta D(q)}{H(h) + \theta D(q)}.$$

Along the family $u_\alpha = (1 - \alpha)q + \alpha h$, specialists' average system knowledge is

$$B_S(\alpha) = q \cdot u_\alpha = (1 - \alpha) \sum_{k=1}^K q_k^2 + \alpha q \cdot h,$$

so

$$B'_S(\alpha) = q \cdot h - \sum_{k=1}^K q_k^2.$$

Using $h_k = q_k(1 - q_k)/D(q)$,

$$q \cdot h = \frac{\sum_k q_k^2 - \sum_k q_k^3}{D(q)},$$

hence

$$B'_S(\alpha) = \frac{(\sum_k q_k^2)^2 - \sum_k q_k^3}{D(q)} \leq 0.$$

By Cauchy–Schwarz, the inequality is strict unless q is uniform.

For integrators,

$$B_M(\alpha) = H(h)^p \mathcal{C}(h, u_\alpha).$$

For each coordinate k , if $h_k \leq q_k$, then $u_{\alpha,k} \geq h_k$ for every α , so $\min\{h_k, u_{\alpha,k}\} = h_k$. If $h_k \geq q_k$, then $u_{\alpha,k} \leq h_k$ for every α , so $\min\{h_k, u_{\alpha,k}\} = u_{\alpha,k}$. Therefore $\mathcal{C}(h, u_\alpha)$ is affine in α , with

$$\frac{d}{d\alpha} \mathcal{C}(h, u_\alpha) = \sum_{k: h_k \geq q_k} (h_k - q_k) = 1 - \mathcal{C}(h, q) \geq 0,$$

where the last equality uses $\sum_k h_k = \sum_k q_k = 1$. The inequality is strict if and only if $h \neq q$, i.e. if and only if q is non-uniform. Hence

$$B'_M(\alpha) = H(h)^p [1 - \mathcal{C}(h, q)] \geq 0,$$

strictly so when q is non-uniform.

Since the productive allocation is fixed along this family, $m^q(\theta)$ and Y^q are constant in

α . Aggregate system knowledge is therefore

$$B^{soc}(\alpha) = (1 - m^q(\theta))B_S(\alpha) + m^q(\theta)B_M(\alpha),$$

so

$$\frac{dB^{soc}}{d\alpha} = (1 - m^q(\theta))\left(q \cdot h - \sum_k q_k^2\right) + m^q(\theta)H(h)^p[1 - \mathcal{C}(h, q)].$$

The first term is strictly negative when q is non-uniform, while the second is strictly positive. Hence the sign of $dB^{soc}/d\alpha$ is in general ambiguous. But $m^q(\theta) \rightarrow 0$ as $\theta \downarrow 0$, so

$$\lim_{\theta \downarrow 0} \frac{dB^{soc}}{d\alpha} = q \cdot h - \sum_k q_k^2 < 0$$

whenever q is non-uniform. Therefore $dB^{soc}/d\alpha < 0$ for all sufficiently small θ .

Turn now to welfare. Along the family $\{u_\alpha\}$, output does not change, so Proposition 4 yields

$$\frac{d\mathcal{W}}{d\alpha} = \frac{\mathcal{R}_B(Y^q, B^{soc}(\alpha))}{\mathcal{R}(Y^q, B^{soc}(\alpha))} \frac{dB^{soc}}{d\alpha} - \frac{d\mathcal{D}}{d\alpha}.$$

The governance term is therefore negative for all sufficiently small θ .

It remains to control the dispersion term. Write $m \equiv m^q(\theta)$. Since

$$\mathcal{D}(\alpha) = \log((1 - m)B_S(\alpha) + mB_M(\alpha)) - (1 - m)\log B_S(\alpha) - m\log B_M(\alpha),$$

differentiating gives

$$\frac{d\mathcal{D}}{d\alpha} = \frac{m(1 - m)(B_M(\alpha) - B_S(\alpha))}{B^{soc}(\alpha)} \left[\frac{B'_M(\alpha)}{B_M(\alpha)} - \frac{B'_S(\alpha)}{B_S(\alpha)} \right].$$

Because $B_S(\alpha)$, $B_M(\alpha)$, $B'_S(\alpha)$, and $B'_M(\alpha)$ are bounded on $[0, 1]$, the derivative $d\mathcal{D}/d\alpha$ is $O(m^q(\theta))$. Hence

$$\frac{d\mathcal{D}}{d\alpha} \rightarrow 0 \quad \text{as} \quad \theta \downarrow 0.$$

Finally, as $\theta \downarrow 0$, we have $m^q(\theta) \rightarrow 0$, $Y^q \rightarrow V$, and $B^{soc}(\alpha) \rightarrow B_S(\alpha)$. Therefore the governance term converges to

$$\frac{\mathcal{R}_B(V, B_S(\alpha))}{\mathcal{R}(V, B_S(\alpha))} B'_S(\alpha) < 0.$$

Combining this strict negative limit with $d\mathcal{D}/d\alpha \rightarrow 0$ implies

$$\frac{d\mathcal{W}}{d\alpha} < 0$$

for all sufficiently small θ . ■

Proof of Proposition 6. Write $h^* \equiv h^*(q)$. By Theorem 1,

$$m^q(\theta) = \frac{\theta D(q)}{H(h^*) + \theta D(q)}, \quad Y^q(\theta) = \frac{VH(h^*)}{H(h^*) + \theta D(q)}.$$

Differentiating gives

$$\frac{dm^q}{d\theta} = \frac{D(q)H(h^*)}{(H(h^*) + \theta D(q))^2} > 0, \quad \frac{dY^q}{d\theta} = -\frac{VH(h^*)D(q)}{(H(h^*) + \theta D(q))^2} < 0.$$

At the productive allocation, B_S^q and B_M^q do not depend on θ , because the specialist profile q and the integrator profile $h^*(q)$ are fixed. Aggregate system knowledge is therefore

$$B^{soc}(\mathcal{A}^q(\theta)) = (1 - m^q(\theta))B_S^q + m^q(\theta)B_M^q,$$

so

$$\frac{d}{d\theta} B^{soc}(\mathcal{A}^q(\theta)) = \frac{dm^q}{d\theta} (B_M^q - B_S^q) > 0$$

by Proposition 1.

Finally, Proposition 4 gives

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d\mathcal{W}(\mathcal{A}^q(\theta))}{d\theta} &= \left[(1 - \tau) + \frac{\mathcal{R}_Y(Y^q(\theta), B^{soc}(\mathcal{A}^q(\theta)))}{\mathcal{R}(Y^q(\theta), B^{soc}(\mathcal{A}^q(\theta)))} \right] \frac{dY^q}{d\theta} \\ &\quad + \frac{\mathcal{R}_B(Y^q(\theta), B^{soc}(\mathcal{A}^q(\theta)))}{\mathcal{R}(Y^q(\theta), B^{soc}(\mathcal{A}^q(\theta)))} \frac{d}{d\theta} B^{soc}(\mathcal{A}^q(\theta)) - \frac{d}{d\theta} \mathcal{D}(\mathcal{A}^q(\theta)). \end{aligned}$$

■